

Inherit

First wave of INHERIT Decision support services/D4.1

WP 4, T 4.1 – 4.4

Authors: Dr Sotirios Aspragkathos (SLG); Iasonas Sotiropoulos (SLG); Carla Rodríguez Alonso (CARTIF); María Esteban Ferrer (CARTIF), Víctor Iván Serna González (CARTIF), Gloria Calleja-Rodríguez (CEMOSA); José María Sanchez-Guerrero (CEMOSA), Evangelos Spiliotis (ICCS), Marina Solovyeva (ICCS), Dimitra Tzani (UPRC); Alexandros Flamos (UPRC); Andrew Barney (UU), Heracles Polatidis (UU); Weiwei Chen (UCL)

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1.0	28/06/2024	SLG	Dr. Sotirios Aspragkathos	First draft of D4.1
1.1	08/07/2024	CEMOSA	Gloria Calleja-Rodríguez	Section 4.3 on Digital Twin

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			Jose María Sanchez Guerrero	for heritage facilities & section 1.3 on technology releases delivery
1.1	08/07/2024	CARTIF	Carla Rodríguez Alonso, María Esteban Ferrer, Víctor Iván Serna González	Input for s.8 and s.10 in the Section 6.1 and 6.3
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1.1	08/07/2024	UU	Andrew Barney, Heracles Polatidis	Input for Section 4.3
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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
D	Deliverable
3D	Three dimensions
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
BGI	Blue-Green Infrastructure
BIM	Building Information Model
BVC	Buldings Value Chain
CDH	Cooling Degree Hours
CGAL	Computational Geometry Algorithms Library
CH	Cultural Heritage
CityGML	City Geography Markup Language
CMIP6	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6
D	Deliverable
DBSCAN	Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise
DB	Database
DT	Digital Twin
DSM	Digital Surface Model
DTM	Digital Terrain Model
EGNSS	European Global Navigation Satellite System
EOSC	European open Science Cloud
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
FDAM	Flood Damage Assessment Methodology
GA	Grant Agreement
gDT	geometric Digital Twin

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GIS	Geographical Information System
GNNS	Graph Neural Networks
GPS	Global Positioning System
IEQ	Indoor Environmental Quality
ML	Machine Learning
UI	User Interface

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Executive Summary

The present document, titled “First wave of INHERIT Decision support services” presents the progress and findings from the beginning of the project regarding WP4 “Decision support services for the heritage-build environment’s life cycle”, addressing tasks and milestones to achieve the objectives of the INHERIT project. The deliverable aims to present and analyze the progress of the basic components of WP4: The definition of a general architecture based on building blocks considering requirements and data modelling, the ensuring of interoperability through Data Spaces compliance, and finally the delivery of the flexible ICT-based decision support services adapted to various CH environments. The work documented in this deliverable aligns with and advances the services aiming for the next generation of solutions for sustainable, inclusive, resource-efficient, and resilient CH, as mentioned above. This phase contributes to the overall project's success by setting milestones through the progress of the services.

The D4.1 deliverable reports on the advancing of the INHERIT project’s objectives by establishing foundational elements for decision support and interoperability within cultural heritage environments. This phase directly supports the project’s mission to create resilient, adaptive, and inclusive solutions for CH management by:

- Decision-making through the interoperable Data Exchange Platform, utilizing data usage across diverse CH assets.
- Tailored services development aiming for design, renovation, monitoring and preservation that align with resource-efficient practices as described in the project’s sustainability/resiliency goals
- Ensuring that the developed services adaptable to various cultural and environmental contexts

1. Introduction

Cultural heritage, encompassing both its tangible and intangible forms, is a vital source of creativity, well-being, identity, and knowledge. This heritage is crucial for tackling contemporary and future challenges. The cultural importance of our traditional and historic buildings is a reflection of our collective identity as communities and individuals, significantly influencing both urban and rural settings. Within the European Union (EU), approximately 21.6% of the building stock predates 1945, with a substantial number of these buildings recognized for their heritage value (Foster, 2020). This rich heritage enhances community life and positions Europe as a leading destination for cultural tourism. Cultural Heritage (CH) sites, as non-transferable assets, foster social cohesion, rejuvenate neighborhoods, boost property values, increase tax revenues, create skilled employment opportunities, and drive economic growth. However, the preservation, restoration, adaptive reuse, interpretation, and management of heritage buildings pose numerous challenges and complexities.

Addressing these challenges necessitates social and transdisciplinary collaboration across various fields and sectors. The multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary nature of the CH sector, with its unique and irreplaceable assets, highlights the importance of focused research and development efforts.

The INHERIT project aspires to co-create, develop, demonstrate, validate, and replicate innovative solutions for sustainable, inclusive, resource-efficient, and resilient cultural heritage. This ambitious vision leverages advanced Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), including the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and big data analytics, alongside evolving social and behavioral practices. Our goal is to enable socially innovative and cost-effective interventions across diverse urban scales, from individual buildings to entire neighborhoods. This comprehensive approach addresses all pertinent aspects of the heritage-built environment's life cycle, encompassing:

Furthermore, by integrating these advanced technologies and practices, we aim to ensure that cultural heritage not only survives but thrives, contributing to the well-being and resilience of our societies. This project seeks to bridge the gap between tradition and innovation, ensuring heritage sites remain vibrant and relevant in the modern world.

Work Package 4 (WP4), titled “Decision Support Services for the Heritage-Built Environment’s Life Cycle”, is focused on achieving the following objectives:

- Develop a comprehensive architecture based on modular building blocks that account for requirements and data models, including user interfaces and APIs, and ensure the integration of foundational technologies and building blocks
- Promote interoperability by adhering to existing Data Spaces initiatives
- Provide adaptable ICT-based decision support services tailored to various CH environments

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Figure 1: The categories of the INHERIT innovative solutions

Through these efforts, INHERIT aims to foster a sustainable future for cultural heritage by leveraging advanced technologies and fostering collaboration across multiple disciplines and sectors.

Specifically, this document covers the initial architecture design/preparation and findings of the basic tasks of WP4 and all the project services that come together with each one of them:

- Task 4.1: Smartification and data exchange platform, tailored to CH and compliant with European Data Spaces (s.0)
- Task 4.2: 'Design & renovation' services (s.1 - s.3)
- Task 4.3: 'Monitoring, operation & management' services (s.4 - s.7)
- Task 4.4 'Preservation & maintenance' services (s.8 - s.10)

The deliverable yields important insights into data exchange, decision support, real-time crowd and environmental monitoring, and finally interventions for building maintenance and building. The key findings presented in the deliverable include:

- The conceptual architecture of the whole WP4 of the INHERIT project and the services composing it
- The first release of the Data Exchange Platform for the INHERIT project
- The first release of the Decision Support Tools of the INHERIT project
- The initial architecture design of the monitoring and operation services of the INHERIT project
- The first release of the 'Preservation & maintenance' services of the INHERIT project

1.1. Conceptual architecture

INHERIT aims to build an open, modular, interoperable platform that will enable the integration and processing of heterogeneous data, allowing the development of added-value services. Figure 2 shows the proposed platform's high-level architecture.

Figure 2: INHERIT High-Level Architecture

Data Acquisition Layer: A baseline core platform will implement the data acquisition and the data management layers of the architecture as shown in Figure 2. The platform will implement interfaces to relevant Copernicus core services, citizen science observatories, and external data sources, such as external data repositories (e.g. open data repositories for demographic data) and IoT data (e.g. actual energy consumption data retrieved by smart meters deployed at buildings).

Data Management: On top of the Data Acquisition Layer, INHERIT will provide a Data Management Layer that is composed of the data integration and storage components of the platform. To address different user needs, the platform architecture will consider different databases, i.e., relational and/or non-relational. In addition, the platform will integrate in this layer a secondary deep storage component. The secondary storage component adds horizontal scalability and flexibility to the data management layer due to its high-performance, S3-compatible object storage.

Data Exchange: The platform will also support trustworthy data exchange by leveraging on standard-compliant connectors (in line with Data Space initiatives) to gather, standardize and make data available to application providers and external stakeholders. The platform will follow an open modular approach, enabling integration with external systems through appropriate RESTful APIs. In this line, INHERIT will offer where applicable client libraries to facilitate the integration with the open APIs and allow external developers to leverage platforms' capabilities. Finally through Data Discovery, the platform allows the querying of INHERIT data catalogues through a common interface.

Identity Management: In addition, INHERIT platform will provide horizontal services related to User Management, Access Control and Data Discovery services. In this line, INHERIT will provide the following mechanisms: 1) Identity management: component for user authentication that would enable user to use data and services based on predefined assigned roles; 2) Access Control: component responsible to check if the user has the rights to access/process/write on specific data.

Data Discovery & AI: The platform will integrate components for the processing and fusion of data, along with appropriate AI-based prediction models.

Data Visualization & Services: At the application level, the platform will deliver services that will allow the visualization of data through dashboards and geo-spatial views. By relying on the underlying data and AI analytics, the platform will deliver decision support services, enabling simulation and analysis of future scenarios.

1.2. Technology releases delivery

The following Table 1 depicts the different developments of the horizontal Data Exchange Platform (see Fig. 1) and the services that will be ready for the three different technology releases. The “Functionalities” column lists the different functionalities for the different elements, with an assigned number that is referenced in the “Releases” columns. Then, in the three columns for the technology releases, the different numbers are referenced to point out the functionalities that will be released in each one. Some clarifications next to the bullet number points are made to make clear if the functionality will be ready for the release but only partly, or with the simplified or initial element.

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Type: 1-Web Service; 2-Infrastructure; 3-BIM Models; 4-Algorithms; 5-Datasets

Tool	Type	Baseline features (if applicable)	Features for the 1 st cycle (1st technology release)
s.0 Data Exchange Platform	2-Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Architecture design & implementation ✓ Microservices development ✓ APIs design & implementation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Identity provisioning ✓ Data storage and data management (upload/download/ update) ✓ Folder functionalities (creation of folders, upload files in certain folders, etc.)
s.1 Interactive screen use and AR VR interfaces for heritage building design and renovation construction	1- Web service 5-Datasets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Architecture design & implementation ✓ Databases & APIs design ✓ BIM (Autodesk) and GIS integration ✓ User-centric interaction design ✓ Real-Time visualization and data integration ✓ Scenario-Based training module development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Establish core system framework that connects hardware with software functionalities ✓ Identify first-pass user interaction features ✓ Identify basic worker training scenarios ✓ Hardware setup and compatibility ✓ Construction of relevant data set (features, images and available 3D models of historical building)
s.2 Modeling and simulation environment	1-Web service 5-Datasets and renovation roadmaps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Architecture design & implementation ✓ Microservices development ✓ User interface design ✓ APIs design 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Collecting and processing data with regards to building features of the pilots to integrate in the model ✓ Architecture design & implementation
s.3 Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	1-Web service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Architecture design & implementation ✓ Database design and development ✓ User interface design ✓ APIs design 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Use of reference data ✓ Result visualization functionality ✓ Preliminary ranking capabilities ✓ Preliminary data entry

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Tool	Type	Baseline features (if applicable)	Features for the 1 st cycle (1st technology release)
s.4 Indoor environmental quality & comfort optimization	1- Web Service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Architecture design & implementation ✓ Database design and development ✓ Microservices development ✓ User interface design ✓ APIs design 	Development of endpoints that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Filter raw data and aggregate results (per room and time interval) ✓ Preprocess data (identify & exclude outliers) ✓ Identify occupancy hours. ✓ Evaluate IEQ parameters based on predefined thresholds.
s.5 Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management	1- Web service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Architecture design & implementation ✓ Database design and development ✓ Microservices development ✓ User interface design ✓ APIs design 	Development of endpoints that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Filter raw data and aggregate results (per room and time interval) ✓ Preprocess data (identify & exclude outliers) ✓ Identify occupancy hours. ✓ Produce energy forecasts for the following week.
s.6 Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real time monitoring and management	1- Web service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Architecture design & implementation ✓ DT Databases & APIs implementation ✓ Microservices development ✓ User interface development ✓ Monitoring data integration (data space) ✓ BIM integration (Autodesk) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Architecture design & implementation

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Tool	Type	Baseline features (if applicable)	Features for the 1 st cycle (1st technology release)
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Calculation engine integration (energyplus) 	
s.7 Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns	1- Web service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Architecture design ✓ Microservices development ✓ APIs design 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Architecture design & implementation ✓ Database design and development ✓ User interface design & development
s.8 Preventive Maintenance with H-BIM	3- BIM Models		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Definition of the methodological needs and requirements to be taken into account for the collection of information during the TI.
s.9 GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	1- Web service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Architecture design & implementation ✓ Database design and development ✓ Microservices development ✓ User interface design ✓ APIs design 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Set of building features to be considered by the clustering algorithm. ✓ Construction of reference data set (images and features of historical buildings).
s.10 Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	1-Web service 5-Maps and datasets		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Definition of the methodological process for the service development, user workflow and architecture.

Table 1: Relation of the platform and services with what will be delivered in each technology release

1.3. Deliverable structure

The present deliverable 4.1 “First wave INHERIT Decision support services” is the first iteration of the Decision support for the heritage-built environment’s life cycle, where the first release is reported: The document is structured in the following sections:

- Section 1, the current section, introduces the INHERIT project, WP4 objectives and concept, services, as well as the methodology. It also includes the document structure ([1.1](#)) and the delivery plan for the three technology releases ([1.2](#)).
- Section 2, presents the runtime environment of the services developed along WP4 Tasks comprised of the Docker containerization technology and its orchestration through Kubernetes.
- Section 3, presents and describes the so far development of s.0 Data Exchange Platform for CH buildings.
- Section 4, presents the progress of the ‘design & renovation’ services (s.1 – s.3)
- Section 5, presents the progress of the ‘monitoring, operation & management’ services (s.4 – s.7)
- Section 6, presents the progress of the ‘preservation & maintenance’ services (s.8 – s.10)

2. Runtime environment

The INHERIT Platform adopts Docker as the core containerization technology, which facilitates the creation of lightweight, self-contained software units encapsulating code and its dependencies. This approach ensures that microservices can run consistently across various computing environments, from development to production. Docker containers are highly portable, making it easy to deploy them on virtual machines, cloud platforms, and personal computers, ensuring maximum flexibility for stakeholders. Docker Desktop provides a user-friendly interface for managing containers, while the Docker Engine handles the execution of containers, supporting a wide range of operating systems including Windows, Linux, and macOS.

Figure 3: Docker repositories related to the INHERIT Exchange Platform

2.1. Container orchestration through Kubernetes

To manage the complexity of deploying and scaling multiple containers, the platform uses Kubernetes for container orchestration. Kubernetes automates the deployment, scaling, and operation of containerized applications, ensuring high availability and efficient resource utilization. The choice of Kubernetes is driven by its cloud-agnostic nature, allowing the platform to be hosted on various cloud services without vendor lock-in. Kubernetes orchestrates the deployment of containers using YAML configuration files, defining the desired state of the system. This setup includes key components such as Deployments, Pods, Replica Sets, Services, and Ingresses, each playing a crucial role in maintaining the platform's operational integrity.

2.1.1. Exchange Platform Pods

In Kubernetes, a pod is the smallest deployable unit and can contain one or more containers that share storage and network resources. Pods are designed to support close collaboration between their containers, facilitating efficient communication and resource sharing. The current INHERIT Kubernetes cluster comprises 22 pods (a screenshot presenting 5 of them is depicted in Figure 4),

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each encapsulating microservices critical to the platform’s functionality. This modular approach ensures that the platform can scale horizontally, adding more pods to handle increased load without affecting performance.

Pods										
Name	Namespace	Images	Labels	Node	Status	Restarts	CPU Usage (cores)	Memory Usage (bytes)	Created ↑	
account-manager-api-fc5cdcbdc-nmgds	oidc	singularlogic/account-manager-api	app: account-manager-api pod-template-hash: fc5cdcbdc	inherit	Running	0	-	-	9.days.ago	⋮
storage-api-app-5b95c5785-zk45x	inherit-storage	singularlogic/storage-api	app: storage-api-app pod-template-hash: 5b95c5785	inherit	Running	0	-	-	9.days.ago	⋮
storage-api-app-5b95c5785-f2kh9	inherit-storage	singularlogic/storage-api	app: storage-api-app pod-template-hash: 5b95c5785	inherit	Running	0	-	-	9.days.ago	⋮
storage-api-app-5b95c5785-bf7e9	inherit-storage	singularlogic/storage-api	app: storage-api-app pod-template-hash: 5b95c5785	inherit	Running	0	-	-	9.days.ago	⋮
minio-5849fbb459j7q8q	inherit-storage	quay.io/minio/minio.latest	app: minio pod-template-hash: 5849fbb459	inherit	Running	0	-	-	11.days.ago	⋮

Figure 4: Screenshot displaying 5 pods of the INHERIT Exchange Platform

2.1.2. Exchange Platform Deployments

Deployments are higher-level abstractions in Kubernetes that manage the lifecycle of pods, including scaling, updating, and rolling back applications. A deployment specifies the desired state of the application, such as the number of pod replicas that should be running. Kubernetes ensures that the actual state matches the desired state, automatically replacing failed pods and updating configurations without downtime. The INHERIT cluster includes 11 deployments (a screenshot presenting 5 of them is shown in Figure 5), each managing different microservices, ensuring seamless updates and high availability. Table 2 presents the YAML file declaring the exchange platform’s deployment in the cluster.

Deployments						
Name	Namespace	Images	Labels	Pods	Created ↑	
storage-api-app	inherit-storage	singularlogic/storage-api	app: storage-api-app	3 / 3	11.days.ago	⋮
minio	inherit-storage	quay.io/minio/minio.latest	app: minio	1 / 1	11.days.ago	⋮
mongodb-deployemnt	inherit-storage	mongo:4.2	-	1 / 1	12.days.ago	⋮
assessment-tool	inherit-assessment	singularlogic/inherit-assessment-tool	app: assessment-tool	2 / 2	29.days.ago	⋮
account-manager-api	oidc	singularlogic/account-manager-api	app: account-manager-api	1 / 1	a.month.ago	⋮

Figure 5: Screenshot displaying 10 deployments of the INHERIT Exchange Platform

<pre>apiVersion: apps/v1 kind: Deployment metadata: name: storage-api-app namespace: inherit-storage labels: app: storage-api-app spec:</pre>	<pre>- name: MINIO_URL value: minio.inherit-storage:9000 - name: OIDC_PROVIDER value: https://keycloak-inherit.euinno.eu/realms/inherit - name: COP_BUCKET_ID value: b3d2feda-5337-490c-b2dd-bbcbbb8f7f0d - name: CLIENT_ID valueFrom:</pre>
---	--

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<pre> replicas: 3 template: metadata: name: storage-api-app labels: app: storage-api-app spec: containers: - name: storage-api image: singularlogic/storage- api ports: - containerPort: 8006 env: - name: ACCESS_KEY valueFrom: secretKeyRef: name: minio-keys key: accessKey - name: SECRET_ACCESS_KEY valueFrom: secretKeyRef: name: minio-keys key: secretAccessKey - name: DATABASE value: minio - name: MONGO_URL value: mongodb://mongodb- service.inherit-storage:27017 </pre>	<pre> secretKeyRef: name: kc-minio-client key: id - name: CLIENT_SECRET valueFrom: secretKeyRef: name: kc-minio-client key: password - name: ADS_UID valueFrom: secretKeyRef: name: secret-ads key: UUID - name: ADS_KEY valueFrom: secretKeyRef: name: secret-ads key: key - name: CDS_UID valueFrom: secretKeyRef: name: secret-cds key: UUID - name: CDS_KEY valueFrom: secretKeyRef: name: secret-cds key: key restartPolicy: Always selector: matchLabels: app: storage-api-app </pre>
--	---

Table 2: YAML file declaring the INHERIT Exchange Platform API deployment

2.1.3. Exchange Platform Services

Kubernetes services provide stable endpoints to access pods, abstracting the underlying complexity of pod management. Services enable load balancing and facilitate communication between different parts of the application or with external clients. The platform currently operates 13 services (a screenshot presenting 5 of them is shown in Figure 6), each corresponding to a specific set of pods. These services ensure that applications remain accessible and performant, distributing traffic evenly and managing network routing efficiently. Table 3 presented the YAML file declaring the exchange platform’s service in the cluster.

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Services							
Name	Namespace	Labels	Type	Cluster IP	Internal Endpoints	External Endpoints	Created ↑
storage-api	inherit-storage	-	ClusterIP	10.104.175.101	storage-api.inherit-storage:80 TCP storage-api.inherit-storage:0 TCP	-	11 days ago
minio	inherit-storage	-	ClusterIP	10.110.235.39	minio.inherit-storage:9090 TCP minio.inherit-storage:0 TCP minio.inherit-storage:9000 TCP minio.inherit-storage:0 TCP	-	12 days ago
mongodb-service	inherit-storage	-	NodePort	10.98.232.232	mongodb-service.inherit-storage:27017 TCP mongodb-service.inherit-storage:30017 TCP	-	12 days ago
tool-service	inherit-assessment	app: assessment-tool	NodePort	10.106.29.237	tool-service.inherit-assessment:80 TCP tool-service.inherit-assessment:30080 TCP	-	29 days ago
account-manager-api	oidc	-	ClusterIP	10.98.105.107	account-manager-api.oidc:80 TCP account-manager-api.oidc:0 TCP	-	a month ago

Figure 6: Screenshot displaying 5 services of the INHERIT Exchange Platform

```

kind: Service
apiVersion: v1
metadata:
  name: storage-api
  namespace: inherit-storage
spec:
  selector:
    app: storage-api-app
  ports:
  - protocol: TCP
    port: 80
    targetPort: 30000
  
```

Table 3: YAML file declaring the INHERIT Exchange Platform API service

2.1.4. Exchange Platform Ingresses

Ingresses in Kubernetes manage external access to services within the cluster, defining rules for routing HTTP and HTTPS traffic to specific services based on domain names and paths. Ingress controllers provide advanced load balancing, SSL termination, and name-based virtual hosting. The INHERIT platform employs 5 ingresses (a screenshot presenting 5 of them is shown in Figure 7), which handle incoming traffic, directing it to the appropriate services based on predefined rules. This setup enhances the platform's security and accessibility, providing a robust mechanism for managing external requests. [Error! Reference source not found.](#) presents the YAML file declaring the core platform's ingress in the cluster.

Ingresses					
Name	Namespace	Labels	Endpoints ↗	Hosts ↗	Created ↑
api-core-ingress	inherit-storage	-	172.31.154.42	api-inherit.euinno.eu	11 days ago
api-minio-ingress	inherit-storage	-	172.31.154.42	minioapi-inherit.euinno.eu	12 days ago
minio-ingress	inherit-storage	-	172.31.154.42	minio-inherit.euinno.eu	12 days ago
assessment-tool-ingress	inherit-assessment	-	172.31.154.42	assesstool-inherit.euinno.eu	29 days ago

Figure 7: Screenshot displaying the ingresses of the INHERIT Exchange Platform

```

apiVersion: networking.k8s.io/v1
kind: Ingress
  
```


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```
metadata:  
  name: api-core-ingress  
  namespace: inherit-storage  
  annotations:  
    kubernetes.io/ingress.class: nginx  
    nginx.org/client-max-body-size: "10m"  
    nginx.ingress.kubernetes.io/proxy-body-size: "10m"  
spec:  
  rules:  
  - host: api-inherit.euinno.eu  
    http:  
      paths:  
      - path: /  
        pathType: Prefix  
      backend:  
        service:  
          name: storage-api  
          port:  
            number: 80
```

Table 4: YAML file declaring the INHERIT Exchange Platform API ingress

3. Smartification and data exchange platform, tailored to CH and compliant with European Data Spaces

The INHERIT data Exchange Platform is designed to enhance the management and exchange of data related to Cultural Heritage (CH) buildings. It employs a streamlined architecture that ensures robust security, efficient data management, and user-friendly interactions. The platform integrates advanced technologies such as Docker and Kubernetes for container orchestration and scalability.

Figure 8: In-depth visualisation of the Exchange Platform's architecture

The primary objective is to provide a high-fidelity software solution that promotes trust in data storage, coupled with advanced access and sharing mechanisms—all encapsulated within a user-friendly experience. To achieve this, the Exchange Platform presents a REST API that serves as an integrator between services and data, implementing also logic for managing files, folders, and sharing mechanisms, ensuring a cohesive and sophisticated user experience. The Exchange Platform follows a three-tier architecture with the following layers: i) identity management (part of the Interconnection block 1); ii) storage; and iii) integration.

3.1. Identity Management Layer

The platform employs OpenID Connect (OIDC) and [Keycloak](#) to handle user authentication and authorization. OIDC provides a secure and standardized method for users to log in using their email and password, extending OAuth 2.0 for authentication purposes. Keycloak serves as the

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central hub for identity management, offering robust authentication and authorization functionalities. Users can leverage existing credentials for secure access to different applications within the platform. Keycloak's group-based authorization enhances access control, allowing users within the same organization to share data seamlessly. Additionally, an administrative REST API, developed in Python, facilitates organizational management tasks such as creating new organizations, adding users, and managing credentials. This API is open-source and designed to be easily integrated with other services, promoting a consistent and secure user experience across the entire ecosystem.

Figure 9: Implementation of Keycloak in the INHERIT ecosystem

Figure 10: Swagger of the Accounts REST API

3.2. Storage Layer

The Storage Layer utilizes MinIO for object storage and MongoDB for metadata management. MinIO is an S3-compatible file system known for its high performance and scalability. It employs parallelization techniques and horizontal scalability by adding new nodes to the cluster. MinIO ensures data security through encryption in transit and at rest, supporting secure communication protocols. Files are stored in multiple parts to enhance confidentiality and security, aligning with the platform's commitment to data privacy. MongoDB, a NoSQL DB, stores metadata associated with these files. Its schema-less design allows for flexibility in handling diverse metadata

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structures, adapting to the platform's evolving needs. MongoDB's advanced query capabilities and organization-centric approach empower users to perform detailed searches based on metadata attributes. This integrated approach between [MinIO](#) and [MongoDB](#) ensures a synchronized workflow, enhancing data management efficiency and reliability.

3.3. Integration Layer

The Integration Layer is powered by a REST API developed in Golang (v1.20.3), which serves as the backbone of the INHERIT Exchange Platform. This API manages core functionalities such as uploading, downloading, and deleting files, creating MinIO buckets, establishing folders for organized content, and executing operations like folder creation, deletion, and sharing. The API ensures seamless communication between the Identity Management and Storage layers, facilitating secure and efficient data handling. It also adheres to OpenAPI standards, providing a standardized interface for data retrieval and manipulation. This ensures that various services can efficiently consume and contribute to the shared data ecosystem. Strict data models, designed and implemented to enhance interoperability, establish a common language for data exchange, ensuring consistency and reducing ambiguity. Future iterations of the Core API will integrate additional services such as Copernicus APIs related to Land, Climate Change, and Atmosphere services, creating a unified and comprehensive data repository. The integration of the EGNSS Galileo service is also planned, enhancing the platform's geospatial and environmental data capabilities.

The image shows a Swagger UI interface for the Exchange Platform's REST API. It is organized into three main sections: Buckets, Files, and Folders. Each section contains a list of API endpoints with their respective HTTP methods and descriptions. The endpoints are color-coded: green for POST, orange for PUT, blue for GET, and red for DELETE. Each endpoint entry includes a dropdown arrow and a lock icon.

Section	Method	Endpoint	Description
Buckets	POST	/bucket	Create bucket.
	DELETE	/bucket/{id}	Delete bucket with all contents.
Files	PUT	/file	Update a file.
	POST	/file	Upload a file.
	GET	/file/{id}	Download a file.
	DELETE	/file/{id}	Delete file by ID.
	GET	/info/file	Get metadata of file.
Folders	GET	/folder	Get folder by id.
	PUT	/folder	Update folder by ID.
	POST	/folder	Create a new folder.
	GET	/folder/list	List folder's items.
	DELETE	/folder/{id}	Delete folder by id.

Figure 11: Swagger of the Exchange Platform's REST API

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```
models.Meta {
  creator      string
               User's ID that created the file

  date_creation string
               Date and time of creation

  description  string
               Array of descriptions for the file

  read         {
    > [...]
    string]
               Array of user ids with reading rights

  tags         {
    > [...]
               Array of tags for the file

  title        {
    > [...]
    string
               Title of the file

  update       {
    description: Array with data that store the updates
    date        string
                 Date and time of update
    user        string
                 User's id that updated
  }

  write        {
    > [...]
    string]
               Array of user ids with writing rights
  }
}
```

Figure 12: Example of the data model of the metadata stored in MongoDB

4. ‘Design & renovation’ services

4.1. Interactive screen use and AR VR interfaces for heritage building design and renovation construction

4.1.1. Description

The main aim of the service is to provide VR- and AR-based for the building design and renovation construction of the cultural heritage buildings, including 1) AR-based maintenance and renovation to improve work quality and reduce maintenance & renovation time, 2) AR-based human-machine interaction to support on-the-job training, and 3) VR-based pre-intervention planning. VR facilitates in-depth exploration of cultural heritages, allowing different stakeholders to engage from multiple perspectives and improving the efficiency of planning and execution. Meanwhile, AR enhances accessibility and provides site staff with an effective means to showcase key elements and areas of interest with minimal effort. The service will be applied to pilot 5 (Poland) and pilot 6 (Spain) to support finding the most optimum renovation solutions.

4.1.2. Service Workflow

4.1.3. Input and Output Data

The input of the service includes:

Building Information Modeling (BIM) Data: Comprehensive details about the building's architecture, structural components, materials, and other attributes.

Energy consumption data: Information on the building's energy use, including but not limited to patterns, peaks, and overall efficiency, gathered through monitoring systems.

Environmental data: Collected in real-time from various sensors embedded in the heritage building, including temperature, humidity, and energy consumption metrics.

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Maintenance/renovation strategies: Various strategies and plans for building maintenance and renovation, including proposed interventions, timelines, and resource allocations. These strategies are fed into the system for evaluation and simulation within the AR/VR environments.

According to the goals, the output of the service includes:

Immersive VR experiences: Virtual representations of the heritage building, allowing different stakeholders to explore and understand its architecture, and experience heritage intervention projects from a variety of perspectives to increase the quality of delivery and making the further planning and execution phases more efficient and effective.

Augmented reality overlays: Real-time, context-sensitive information displayed on AR devices, assisting with on-the-job training, maintenance, and renovation tasks by highlighting critical areas and providing step-by-step guidance.

Maintenance/renovation simulations: Visual simulations of different maintenance and renovation strategies within the AR/VR environments, allowing stakeholders to assess potential impacts, costs, and outcomes before implementation. Maintenance personnel can also use these simulations as a training tool, familiarizing themselves with the specific tasks and procedures required for the implementation of the chosen strategies.

4.1.4. Internal Architecture

The overall methodology is presented in Figure 13. To achieve the goals, the AR/VR interfaces for heritage building design and renovation construction can be implemented following four main steps:

1. Raw data acquisition, including the BIM model for the heritage buildings and their relevant information such as heating or ventilation system
2. Construction of VR scenario for different stakeholders to interact and for renovation strategies to display
3. Construction of AR scenario, which can enable human-machine interaction and analysis for the renovation strategies
4. Pilot application to find the most optimum renovation solutions for Pilot 5 and Pilot 6

Figure 13: Overall

1. Raw Data Acquisition

2. VR Scenario Construction

3. AR Scenario Construction

4. Pilot Application

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methodology of the interactive screen use and AR VR interfaces for heritage building design and renovation construction

In this project, the system architecture is designed with three main layers: the physical layer, the data layer, and the application layer. Each layer works in tandem to ensure the efficient operation and management of the heritage building project. The system architecture is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: The system architecture of the service

1. The **physical layer** forms the foundation of the system and includes AR and VR devices, as well as various sensors installed within the building. AR devices, such as Microsoft HoloLens 2, provide augmented reality experiences that support on-the-job training and maintenance tasks directly on-site. VR devices offer immersive virtual environments for building showcases and other virtual activities. Additionally, sensors within the building monitor real-time conditions, such as temperature, humidity, and energy consumption, providing essential data to the data layer.
2. The **data layer** serves as the system's core, integrating multiple data sources, including BIM data (including structures and attributes), energy consumption data, and environmental sensor data. This layer not only supports the applications used in the system but also provides real-time and historical data for decision-making. BIM data is particularly important, containing detailed information about the building's structure, design, maintenance records, and material specifications. This comprehensive dataset underpins the AR and VR applications, ensuring they are accurate and contextually relevant.

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3. The **application layer** is where different stakeholders interact with the system's capabilities, encompassing various AR and VR-based application modules. VR technology enables users to explore the heritage building in a virtual environment, allowing for an intuitive understanding of its history and evolution. AR-based applications are used for on-the-job training, providing staff with real-time guidance and feedback in their actual work environments, thus improving efficiency and safety. Additionally, AR is employed in maintenance and renovation tasks, helping maintenance personnel identify and address issues more effectively, which optimizes maintenance processes. The application layer ensures that all interactions are user-centric, focusing on enhancing the experiences and outcomes for the stakeholders involved, and the most optimum renovation solutions can be found.

4.1.5. Implementation

4.1.5.1. Physical Layer

The Physical Layer of the system architecture is the foundational layer that includes the essential hardware components used to interact with and experience the digital environments and data. This layer encompasses both the VR and AR devices, as well as the sensors embedded within the heritage building.

For immersive VR experiences, the system utilizes the HTC Vive Pro (dual AMOLED 3.5-inch diagonal screen, 1440 × 1600 pixels per eye, and 90 Hz refresh rate). This high-resolution VR headset provides an expansive field of view and superior visual clarity, crucial for detailed and engaging virtual simulations of heritage buildings. The Vive Pro's precise tracking capabilities, facilitated by external base stations, allow users to navigate and interact within a virtual environment with high accuracy. This is particularly beneficial for detailed architectural visualizations, historical recreations, and interactive training scenarios.

The AR experience is delivered through Microsoft HoloLens 2. This advanced AR headset is designed to overlay digital content onto the real world, allowing users to interact with holograms and contextual information seamlessly. The HoloLens 2's high-resolution display and advanced spatial mapping capabilities enable users to visualize and manipulate digital data in the context of their physical environment. This is particularly useful for on-site training, maintenance, and renovation tasks, where real-time guidance and interactive overlays provide practical assistance. The device's gesture recognition and voice command features enhance usability, allowing for intuitive interactions without the need for physical controllers.

In addition to the VR and AR devices, the physical layer also includes a network of sensors embedded within the heritage building (if applicable). These sensors monitor environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, and energy consumption, providing crucial data that feeds into the system. This data helps ensure that both the VR and AR applications are working with up-to-date and accurate information, enhancing the relevance and effectiveness of the simulations and interactive experiences. The integration of these sensors with the VR and AR

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systems supports a comprehensive approach to heritage management, combining immersive technology with real-time environmental monitoring.

4.1.5.2. Data Layer

The data layer is the core of the system, responsible for managing, processing, and integrating diverse data sources into a coherent framework that supports the AR and VR applications. This layer ensures that data from various origins—whether it’s BIM models, environmental sensors, or user interaction data—can be seamlessly transferred, interpreted, and utilized across the system.

Data transfer and interoperability: Data in this project comes from a variety of sources, including BIM files, sensor data, and energy consumption records, often stored in different formats and managed by different systems. To ensure smooth data transfer and interoperability, the project employs middleware that converts and standardizes data formats into a unified system that can be easily accessed by the AR and VR platforms. For example, BIM models, which are typically in formats like IFC or Revit, are processed and converted into 3D models compatible with Unity, the development platform used for creating the VR and AR experiences. Figure 15 presents the flowchart of how to integrate different sources of data into Unity environment. Additionally, APIs are used to facilitate real-time data transfer between the building’s sensors and the Unity-based applications, ensuring that all data is current and accurately reflects the physical environment.

Figure 15: Flowchart of creating virtual environment in Unity based on multi-source data

Data visualization and development in Unity: Unity is the primary platform used for developing the VR and AR applications in this project. Once the data from BIM models, environmental sensors, and other sources is integrated and processed, it is visualized within Unity. This platform allows developers to create interactive, 3D environments where users can explore the heritage building in VR or view augmented overlays in AR. Unity’s robust toolset based on C# programming language supports the high-resolution rendering of architectural details, the simulation of real-world physics, and the incorporation of interactive elements, all of which are crucial for effective data visualization. The platform’s flexibility also allows for the seamless integration of real-time data, such as sensor readings or energy consumption stats (also using C# programming language), into the visualizations, providing users with a dynamic and immersive experience that is both informative and engaging.

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Data consistency and accuracy: Version control systems are also implemented to track changes to the data, allowing for rollback if needed and ensuring that all stakeholders are working with the most up-to-date information. This approach minimizes discrepancies between the virtual models and the actual physical building, thereby enhancing the reliability and effectiveness of the AR and VR applications.

4.1.5.3. Application Layer

The application layer is the interface where users engage with the system, leveraging the data processed in the data layer and the hardware provided by the physical layer. This layer is responsible for delivering a variety of applications tailored to the needs of different stakeholders and the two pilots in Poland and Spain, including VR-based building visualizations, AR-assisted training, and maintenance and renovation tools. Developed using Unity, these applications provide an interactive and immersive experience that enhances understanding, training efficiency, and maintenance effectiveness. The system is being piloted in two distinct locations: a heritage building in Poland and another in Spain, allowing for tailored application of the technology in different cultural and architectural contexts.

Firstly, the VR interface. One of the key applications within this layer is the VR-based tool. Developed in Unity, this interface allows users to explore highly detailed, 3D representations of the heritage buildings in Poland and Spain within a virtual environment. These visualizations are created using BIM data and enhanced by real-time environmental data, offering users an accurate and immersive experience. Stakeholders, such as architects, historians, and visitors, can virtually walk through the buildings, examine their architectural features, and view historical reconstructions. This VR interface also supports scenario simulations, where users can visualize potential changes to the buildings or explore different time periods, gaining insights into their evolution and future conservation needs. The pilot projects in Poland and Spain allow for the testing of these VR visualizations in diverse architectural settings, ensuring the tool's versatility and effectiveness.

Secondly, the AR interface. The AR-assisted training interface is another critical component of the application layer. Utilizing Microsoft HoloLens 2 and developed in Unity, this interface overlays digital information onto the physical environment, providing staff with real-time guidance and instructions while they perform tasks. For instance, in the Polish pilot, maintenance personnel can use the AR headset to view step-by-step instructions for repairing specific parts of the building, with visual cues highlighting the exact areas of interest.

The application layer also includes specialized AR-enabled interface for maintenance and renovation, designed to assist planners and engineers in managing the upkeep of the heritage buildings in Poland and Spain. These applications, also built in Unity, utilize AR to project maintenance plans directly onto the building's physical structures. Users can interact with these projections, viewing proposed renovations or repairs in situ before any physical work begins. This allows for better planning and decision-making, as stakeholders can assess the visual and structural impact of different strategies in a real-world context.

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Figure 16: The tech stack for the AR/VR interface development

4.2. Modeling and simulation environment

4.2.1. Description

The main aim of the ‘Modeling and simulation environment’ service is to develop integrated renovation roadmaps for the INHERIT cultural heritage buildings, including different energy efficient measures and financing aspects. The service consists of a user interface that will facilitate the data collection from the users and their interactions with the service and from a simulation tool, the DREEM¹ model.

¹ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0196890419313469>

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Figure 17: Visualisation of the ‘Modeling and simulation environment’ service architecture

The primary objective of the service is to facilitate the decision-making process of the CH building owners/ users with regards to their building’s renovation considering the energy consumption and the related costs of interventions. To achieve this, the Exchange Platform is implemented following 7 main steps:

1. Collection of data related to building characteristics and energy consumption related data.
2. Creating the dynamic energy simulation model of the building before interventions (baseline)
3. Calibrating the model using the data collected for the building
4. Collecting the preferences of building interventions (a checklist of possible renovation actions has been deployed)
5. Simulating the energy efficient scenarios
6. Conducting the technoeconomic assessment
7. Wrapping up the possible renovation actions with potential costs into concrete renovation roadmaps

4.2.2. Service Workflow

4.2.3. Input and Output Data

The tool gets the following input data:

- Building characteristics (Information about the building characteristics (e.g., size of windows, walls, heating systems, etc.)
- Energy efficiency measures catalogue (Information regarding the renovation actions to be simulated)

The tool gets the following output data:

- Energy consumption of the building (baseline), energy savings achieved through the actions explored. The users will have the opportunity to see how different energy actions will impact on the energy consumption of the building.

4.2.4. Internal Architecture

4.2.4.1. Simulation tool

DREEM is a hybrid bottom-up model that combines the key features of both statistical and engineering models. That practically means that it uses both mathematical analysis and statistical assumptions to generate sample data and make predictions about the real world and physics modules that facilitate the simulation of real-life applications. The model serves as an entry point in demand-side modelling in the building sector, by expanding the computational capabilities of existing building simulation models to assess the benefits and limitations of demand-flexibility, primarily for consumers (e.g. building owners and occupants, energy communities, etc.) and for other power actors (e.g. DSOs, TSOs, energy providers) involved.

The DREEM model consists of multiple components, each of which is composed of additional modules. The overall architecture of the model, as visualised in [Error! Reference source not found.](#), makes it flexible to be adapted, modified, and extended in the future. All the modules of the model were developed using the “Buildings” library², which is an open-source, freely available Modelica library for building energy and control systems. Modelica is an equation-based, object-oriented modelling language for the simulation of dynamic systems, and has been used in several studies and applications for the design and simulation of various building energy and control systems. Alongside the Modelica models, Python scripts have been developed to model parts of the DR and control components and to enable the interface with the Dymola simulation environment.

² <https://simulationresearch.lbl.gov/modelica/releases/latest/help/Buildings.html>

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Figure 18: The architecture of the DREEM model

The service will be applied to Pilot 2 (France), Pilot 4 (Latvia), Pilot 8 (Turkey), and replicated to Pilot 7 (Sweden). A simulation model of a residential building in Attica, Greece is presented in Figure 1919.

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Figure 19: Simulation environment in Dymola showing the model of a residential building in Attica, Greece.

4.2.5. Implementation

4.2.5.1. User Interface

The web application consists of a front-end made with React (JS) and a back-end made with the Laravel framework (PHP). The front-end pages are styled with the help of the Tailwind CSS framework. The user authentication is handled by Laravel Sanctum and requires an email address and a password to log users in. The application's data is stored in a MySQL database and the application itself is served using nginx. The backend communicates with the database through the Eloquent ORM (object-relational mapper). The application translations get automatically generated using the DeepL API and the Google Cloud Translation API, for languages that are not yet supported by DeepL.

Figure 20. Screenshot displaying the creation of the user profile

After creating the user profile, the users are required to provide information regarding the building characteristics as presented below.

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Welcome to the Dynamic high-Resolution dEmand-side Management (DREEM) model Data Collection Platform.
 In this form, you will insert the general characteristics of the building for your case study.

Building profile title
 E.g. University of Piraeus main buildings

Country *
 E.g. Greece

Region *
 E.g. Peloponnese

Please provide a valid email address where you will receive the simulation results and the researchers can get in touch with you.

Construction year *
 --- select timeframe ---

Contact information (email)
 aexint@unipi.gr

Building Area (m²) *
 Occupancy (ppl)

Occupants' indicative working schedule

Workdays	Weekends
From	From
To	To

Other information

Figure 21: Screenshot displaying the main information of the building profile required

Welcome to the Dynamic high-Resolution dEmand-side Management (DREEM) model Data Collection Platform.
 In this form, you will insert the envelope characteristics of the building for your case study.

Walls *

Wall 1 surface (m²) *
 1

Wall 1 U value (W/m²/K)
 1

Roofs *

Floors *

Windows

Previous Next

Figure 22: Screenshot displaying the technical characteristics of the building required

After completing the information required from the building users we extract the inputs in a .csv file and the development of the simulation environment is proceeded.

4.3. Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning

4.3.1. Description

Historic buildings have properties and qualities that must be preserved when refurbishing or reusing a building. Suitable renovation measures are, however, limited due to the heritage values represented in these buildings. At the same time, a number of economic, resource, environmental, and societal parameters and criteria should be taken into account in order to identify, select, and implement the optimal renovation strategy for cultural historical buildings. To this end, several European projects and initiatives have worked towards providing decision support for selecting renovation and measures in historic buildings. Nevertheless, the methods proposed tend to be only instrumental and overly simplified rather than addressing the fundamental questions of how complex multi-criteria decisions are made in current practice, and how informed decisions could be facilitated. Within the context of this project, a decision support tool for optimal renovation planning based on explicit multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) methods is developed using pertinent renovation options and analysis of these options' performances given identified relevant criteria.

This decision support tool for optimal renovation planning for cultural heritage buildings could be based on outranking multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) methods. This specific group of MCDA methods is best suited for group decision aiding energy and environmental decision problems since they decompose the problem into measurable attributes and encompass a non-compensatory criteria aggregation algorithm that supports a strong sustainability concept. This means that a very poor performance of a possible alternative to one criterion cannot be fully compensated by a very good performance in another criterion. In that way, critical environmental and cultural values can be preserved (Polatidis, 2006).

This tool will allow the application of a MCDA methodological framework to improve the condition of the historical buildings through efficient decision-making for optimal renovation considering environmental, economic, cultural heritage and societal factors as well as stakeholders' needs.

4.3.2. Service Workflow

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4.3.3. Input and Output Data
4.3.3.1. Input data

This tool will rely on already existing data sets to establish the performance of different renovation options. The set of potential renovation options will be selectable by users from the relevant Inherit database while the criteria by which to evaluate these options will be selected by users from the INHERIT criteria database. The service user will be prompted to provide their preference thresholds on each criterion or the values at which the user begins to perceive differences between two alternatives being compared for a criterion (indifference threshold) and when the user perceives the differences between two alternatives to be sufficiently large that one alternative is strongly preferred (preference threshold). As a final step, the user will provide weights, using a 100-point system, to each of the criteria used to evaluate the renovation options to indicate each's relative importance in the evaluation. The user may enter several different weights representing the viewpoints of different stakeholders at this stage (Haralambopoulos D., 2003).

The following datasets are expected to be relevant for most or all renovation options.

Dataset	Description
Energy balance sheet for heating: input – output analysis	Heat demand: type and amount of energy used to cover heat demand
Energy balance sheet for cooling: input – output analysis	Cooling demand: type and amount of energy used to cover cooling demand
Energy balance sheet for electrical appliances: input – output analysis	Electrical appliances demand: amount of energy used to cover electrical appliances demand
Energy balance sheet for hot water demand: input – output analysis	Hot water demand: type and amount of energy used to cover hot water demand

Table 5: Datasets for renovation options

List of items: Heat demand assessment; cooling demand assessment; electrical appliances demand assessment; hot water demand assessment; potential renovation measures will be identified together with their environmental impact and implementation cost; data base of wider societal actors' (users, stakeholders, decision-makers, shadow players, ...) preferences will be established via interviews, surveys, focus groups, etc. A simple example of how the user input data base page could look is presented in Figure 23 below.

CASE-STUDY Example: CH renovation project selection problem		Please define here your Scenario, Criteria, Preference Thresholds, Decision Makers and their Weights!				
Scenario		Criteria				
		Evaluation criteria				
		Energy/Technology	Environment	Impact on users' comfort	Economic Cost	
		KWh saved /yr	avoided CO2 / yr	Qualitative: 1-10	€	
		max	max	max	min	
1	Scenario 1: Replacement of windows	2 300	230,00	8,00	30000	
2	Scenario 2: Ceiling insulation	4 100	400,00	5,00	6700	
3	Scenario 3: Installation of heat pumps	7 000	670,00	7,00	50000	
4	Scenario 4: Crack sealing	1 200	140,00	3,00	5000	
		Preference Threshold				
		1 450,00	132,50	1,25	11 250,00	
		Decision-Makers - DMs				
		Weights				
		DM 1: Property manager	25	25	25	SUM 100
		DM 2: Property user	10	70	10	100

Figure 23: User data input page visualisation/example

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4.3.3.2. Output data

Depending on the method chosen by the service user, different outputs are possible from the service. These outputs include a ranking, selection or categorification of the selected renovation options. A brief description of these outputs is provided below.

Ranking - Using the users' inputs, the different renovation options are ranked from the most preferred option to the least preferred option.

Selection - Using the users' inputs, the most suitable alternative from the given renovation options is identified.

Categorization - Using the users' inputs, the given renovation options are categorized.

Sensitivity analysis - The service user will be able to perform sensitivity analyses on the results of the MCDA using three different methods. The user will be able to evaluate how changes in the renovation options' *performances* in a single or across several of the given criteria impact the results. Further, the service user may adjust the *thresholds* provided as well as the *weights* provided to evaluate any changes in the provided results. These adjustments may be made manually by the user or by selecting pre-generated levels of adjustments, i.e., 10% adjustments to criteria performances, thresholds based on calculated average values, or standardized weight allocations. Simple ranking examples can be found in Figures 24 to 27 below.

Figure 24: Visualisation of decision-maker 1's scenario rankings.

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Figure 25: Decision-maker 2's scenario rankings

Figure 26: Decision-maker 3's scenario rankings.

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Figure 27: Decision-maker 4's scenario rankings.

4.3.4. Internal Architecture

An example of the internal service architecture can be found at Figure 28 below.

Figure 28: Preliminary service architecture.

4.3.5. Implementation

At this stage of the project, the efforts have been focused in analyzing the multi-objective criteria to be considered for the INHERIT project and the potential ranking algorithms that may be used for the realization of the tool. In the next phase of the project, the technical partners will further discuss on how the tool can be implemented as part of the INHERIT services. The results of this technical discussions will be documented in the next deliverable D4.2.

5. ‘Monitoring, operation & management’ services

5.1. Indoor environmental quality & comfort optimization

5.1.1. Description

The aim of the service is to exploit the data collected at pilot sites (s.0) using data-driven models, as well as advanced data analytics and reporting techniques, to quantify and evaluate the overall IEQ of the CH buildings, including thermal comfort, air quality, acoustic comfort, and visual comfort. The service leverages results from the BD4NRG and DigiBUILD projects, where relevant approaches have been developed to enhance the well-being of building occupants, putting however particular emphasis on the preservation of the historic assets of the buildings and the feedback received by the users. More specifically, the service supports the assessment of the IEQ across its different components in key areas of the buildings, the detection of anomalies and bad practices, and the proposal of changes in building occupants’ behaviour and building’s operational settings that balance health and safety with energy consumption. The service will be applied to pilot 3 (Greece) and pilot 4 (Latvia) and replicated to pilot 1 (Croatia) and pilot 7 (Sweden).

5.1.2. Service Workflow

5.1.3. Input & Output Data

The input data for this service are as follows:

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Energy consumption for heating and cooling (The data should illustrate for each building area of interest the hours the heating/cooling system(s) operated and the energy consumed for that purpose).

Variables related to IEQ (The data should illustrate for each building area of interest and at hourly level the quantities required for computing IEQ variables (e.g. temperature, humidity, CO2 concentration, noise level).

Variables related to outdoor environmental conditions (The data should illustrate at hourly level key variables related to outdoor environmental conditions that help extract insights about the factors that influence IEQ (e.g. outdoor temperature, noise level).

Feedback of building occupants (Answers provided by building occupants about their comfort and the IEQ.)

The output of the service may include one or more of the following:

1. Detailed measurements of IEQ components and relevant assessments.
2. List of hours and days where anomalies and bad practices have been identified.
3. Recommendations about the hours the heating/cooling system should operate to improve thermal comfort during occupancy hours. This includes pre-heating actions and proposals about the set point temperature to be used.
4. Insights based on historical analysis data about the spaces that are most suitable for working, meeting, etc. per period (e.g. time of the day or month).
5. Proposals about measures that could improve IEQ in terms of both operational and behavioural changes.

5.1.4. Internal Architecture

The service will be exposed to the user through an online GUI, which can be conveniently accessed via standard web browsers. The front-end and the back-end will be interconnected through APIs, with a relational database serving as the repository for managing IEQ information. For the front-end the technology that will probably be used is *Angular*, supplemented by various libraries. For the back-end, *.NET* will be used, complementing *Python* for the algorithms, and supported with other libraries, such as *fastAPI*. To enhance deployment and scalability, the service will be encapsulated within a Docker image, ensuring efficient and consistent deployment across diverse environments.

The service relies on REST API to manage core functionalities, such as parameters setting and fetching the desired data to provide analytical reports. The scripts are executed in Python. For data storage, PostgreSQL is used. Data visualization, reports, and analytical representations are performed in the frontend using React, an open-source UI library executed with TypeScript programming language. The connection between the Database Layer and the Application Layer adopts Docker as the core containerization technology.

Overall, the service follows a three-layer architecture where the components described above are interconnected as follows:

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Figure 29: In-depth visualisation of s.4 architecture.

5.1.5. Implementation

5.1.5.1. Database layer

The Database Layer utilizes PostgreSQL (often referred to as Postgres), which is a powerful, open-source relational database management system (RDBMS) known for its robustness, scalability, and standards compliance. The DB supports a wide range of data types and advanced features, such as multi-version concurrency control (MVCC), which ensures high performance and data integrity. PostgreSQL's extensibility also allows users to define custom functions and data types, making it highly adaptable to various applications. Additionally, it offers strong support for ACID (Atomicity, Consistency, Isolation, Durability) properties, ensuring reliable transaction processing.

The DB is structured to store and manage IEQ-related data across the various rooms of the pilots. Its structure is summarized as follows:

1. **rooms_table**: This table contains information about each room, focusing on its location within the pilot building. Thus, it provides key details about the place each sensor is located.
2. **bounds_table**: Linked to the 'rooms_table', this table defines the acceptable ranges of the various IEQ variables measured in each room. Therefore, it ensures that all IEQ components remain within specified limits (e.g. so that the CH assets are preserved).
3. **reference_table**: Details the sensors deployed in each room, specifying the type of data collected by each sensor.
4. **history_table**: Stores sensor readings along with timestamps. This allows for historical analysis of the IEQ data over time.
5. **working_hours_table**: Generated by the Application Layer, this table records the working hours associated with each pilot based on total energy consumption. This information is critical for evaluating IEQ during the hours that the building is actually occupied.

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The aforementioned DB structure enables comprehensive management and historical tracking of IEQ data, supporting the optimization of conditions within the pilot buildings. For practical reasons, the data included in the BD can be grouped into three main categories based on their origin and purpose, namely Reference Mapping Data, Historical Sensor Data, and Generated Data, as described in the following sections.

Figure 30: Visualisation of s.4 DB schema.

5.1.5.2. Reference Mapping Data

The Reference Mapping Data category includes information that links sensors to specific rooms (stored in the 'reference_table') and mapping rooms to their locations within each pilot project (managed by the 'rooms_table').

In the 'reference_table' of the DB schema, the primary key is 'sensor_id'. This table holds details about each sensor, including its unique identifier, name, and the specific metric of measurement. It is important to distinguish ids from metrics because some sensors can capture multiple metrics simultaneously (e.g. temperature and humidity). If this differentiation isn't provided by the sensor supplier, preprocessing occurs within the Application Layer to conduct the relevant. Additional columns in this table include 'room_id', linking each sensor to its location within a room, and 'metric_units', specifying the units of measurement for each metric.

The 'room_id' in the 'reference_table' corresponds to entries in the 'rooms_table', establishing a relationship between sensors and the rooms where they are installed. The 'rooms_table' primarily focuses on rooms location within the pilot building.

Lastly, the 'bounds_table' defines acceptable ranges for each metric within specific rooms. Its primary key is dual, encompassing both 'metric' and 'room_id', reflecting potential differences in

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metric tolerance based on room type. For example, an office space and a living room may have different acceptable ranges for some of the metrics.

5.1.5.3. Historical Sensor Data

The Historical Sensor Data category consist of one table, 'history_table', that includes time series records of various environmental metrics captured by sensors at regular intervals. It is used for the comprehensive monitoring of IEQ and development of detection algorithms, as well as for pattern extraction and analysis.

The primary key of the 'history_table' consists of two columns: timestamp (stored as 'datetime') and 'sensor_id'. This composite key uniquely identifies each record in the table, ensuring that each entry is distinct and can be reliably referenced. 'Sensor_id', linked to 'reference_table', includes information about both the sensor itself and the specific metric being recorded.

Overall, the data set enables tracking and evaluating environmental conditions over time, identifying trends, and facilitating predictive analytics. By maintaining a detailed log of sensor data, the data set supports advanced data analysis, forecasting, and anomaly detection, contributing to the overall effectiveness of the service.

5.1.5.4. Generated Data

The last category, Generated Data, also consists of one table, 'working_hours_table'. It is created through interaction with the Application Layer, and it is used by the same layer in the analyses and forecasts. The working hours detection algorithm requires electricity consumption data to analyse user's behaviour and mark the hours when the building is assumed to be occupied and, therefore, IEQ is of higher importance.

Further on, this category may include other additional tables, such as flags for cases identified as 'anomalies' that would allow data analysis in real-time.

5.1.5.5. Application layer

The Application Layer consists of Python scripts, organized as a backend for the service. It acts as an intermediary between the Database and Presentation layers, connecting various data processes through a REST API and some relevant SQL queries. In the following screenshot, the structure of the backend is presented:

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Figure 31: Visualisation of s.4 backend structure.

The main components of the Application Layer are presented in the following sections.

5.1.5.6. Database communication

This component includes the 'crud' folder, which contains functions for creating, reading, updating, and deleting (CRUD) DB contents, and the 'models' folder, which describes the structure of each DB table. Each folder contains three primary files, aside from the `__init__.py` file: 'data.py', 'desc.py', and 'generated.py'. The 'data.py' file handles Historical Sensor data, 'desc.py' deals with

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Reference Mapping tables, while the 'generated.py' is responsible for Generated tables, such as the 'working_hours_table'.

The functions within these folders are based on SQLAlchemy, an SQL toolkit and Object-Relational Mapping (ORM) library for Python. SQLAlchemy provides a list of persistence patterns, designed for efficient and high-performing DB access. The application benefits from an abstraction layer that allows for seamless interaction with the DB, ensuring that the CRUD operations and data models are defined in a clear and consistent manner. For example, the code below fetches the historical data of any specified sensor:

```
def get_history_sensor(db: Session, sensor_id: str) -> List[HistoryTable]:  
    """  
    Returns the records for the specified sensor_id.  
  
    :param db: A sqlalchemy.orm.session.Session object.  
    :param sensor_id: The ID of the sensor to fetch records for.  
    :return: A HistoryTable list of objects, time series data.  
    """  
    return db.query(HistoryTable).filter(HistoryTable.sensor_id == sensor_id).all()
```

Finally, the 'database.py' file contains the SQL Alchemy engine to connect to the DB and in '.env' file the DB's port, user, and location are kept.

5.1.5.7. Data analysis

The second component includes the whole folder 'routes' that consists of endpoints connected through the REST API to the frontend. Also, some functions that are used to perform data aggregation, transformations, calculations, and prepare the reported information, such as 'liveview_graphs.py' and 'patters_graphs.py'.

This component is mainly responsible for the Application Layer's communication with the Presentation Layer, as the final reported data is transformed to .json format to be used in the frontend.

5.1.5.8. Insights extraction

The Insights Extraction component leverages results from the BD4NRG and DigiBUILD projects, where advanced data-based models have been integrated to develop services aimed at enhancing comfort and well-being.

The service identifies common issues and proposes targeted actions, to be categorized into soft measures, behavioural changes, and renovations. This structured approach ensures that users receive precise and practical advice to improve IEQ, thereby promoting a healthier and more comfortable living and working environment.

5.1.5.9. Detection algorithms

These functions are declared in 'detection_functions.py' and they are used to identify particular entities, patterns of behavioural change or anomalies within data. Currently these algorithms include working hours and anomaly detection mechanism. The output of the working hours detection algorithm is saved in the DB in the 'working_hours_table' table, while the anomaly detection is currently performed on the fly, as it requires much less time than the former algorithm.

5.1.5.10. REST API

The REST API in the IEQ services is implemented using the FastAPI library, which serves as the conduit between the backend processes and the frontend Presentation Layer. FastAPI is a modern, high-performance web framework for building APIs with Python. It offers automatic interactive API documentation, efficient performance, and support for asynchronous programming that allows for efficient handling of multiple concurrent requests, enhancing the application's responsiveness and scalability.

FastAPI endpoints are used to handle HTTP requests for data retrieval with various parameters, set by the user. These endpoints ensure that data is correctly queried from the DB, processed as needed, and returned in a format that the frontend can easily consume, typically .json. This setup allows for real-time interaction and seamless data transfer.

Since the primary purpose of the aforementioned endpoints is to fetch and display data (such as sensor readings, room statistics, and identified issues), GET requests are the most appropriate method. They allow clients to request data without the risk of modifying or corrupting it. GET requests are inherently safe and idempotent, meaning they do not alter the state of the server and can be called multiple times without side effects.

Currently, the developed endpoints include:

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FastAPI 0.1.0 OAS 3.1
/openapi.json

Common Endpoints		^
GET	/api/rooms/24/common/get_room_sensors	Get Room Sensors Api
GET	/api/rooms/24/common/get_all_sensors	Get All Sensors Api
GET	/api/rooms/24/common/get_all_rooms	Get All Rooms Api
Room Patterns		^
GET	/api/rooms/24/patterns/graph_1	Graph 1 Api
GET	/api/rooms/24/patterns/graph_2	Graph 2 Api
Room Live View		^
GET	/api/rooms/24/live-view/live-graph	Live Graph
GET	/api/rooms/24/live-view/stats	Get Statistics For Room
Room Insights		^
GET	/api/rooms/24/insights/issues	Room Identified Issues
GET	/api/rooms/24/insights/proposals	Room Proposed Actions

Figure 32: Swagger of s.4 REST API.

In the above screenshot, the endpoints are separated in 4 groups – Common endpoints return lists of sensors in specific room or rooms, Room Patterns perform data analysis based on historical data and set parameters, Room Live View returns the latest graph data and latest room statistics, while Room Insights identifies current peaks and issues and proposes actions to optimize the IEQ metrics.

For the endpoints mentioned above, different sets of parameters are required to produce specific results. For example, the endpoint that returns .json formatted data for the live graph visualization is:

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Room Live View ^

GET /api/rooms/24/live-view/live-graph Live Graph ^

Parameters Try it out

Name	Description
dropdown_var * required string <small>(query)</small>	Variable type <i>Available values</i> : Temperature, Humidity Temperature
dropdown_sen * required string <small>(query)</small>	Sensor type <i>Available values</i> : All, th 24, ac 24 All
room_id * required string <small>(query)</small>	Room ID room_id
exclude_anomalies boolean <small>(query)</small>	Exclude anomalies <i>Default value</i> : true true

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response	No links
	Media type <input type="text" value="application/json"/> <small>Controls Accept header.</small> Example Value Schema <pre>{ "datetime": "2024-06-17T14:03:41.085Z", "value": 0 }</pre>	
422	Validation Error	No links

Figure 33: Swagger of s.4 REST API – Room Live View.

In the picture above the first section of the endpoint refers to the parameters that will be set by user. In this case, user will have to choose the desired variable (metric), sensor (or keep 'All' that is the default value). Additionally, 'room_id' will be set automatically, based on the chosen room. Anomaly detection algorithm here is utilized as a binary choice.

5.1.5.11. Docker

Docker is a platform that automates the deployment of applications inside lightweight, portable containers. It works by encapsulating an application and its dependencies into a container, ensuring consistent environments across development, testing, and production.

For the connection of the Database and Application layers, Docker simplifies setup and management by allowing DB to run in isolated containers. This ensures that the DB environment is consistent across different stages of development and deployment. Docker containers are built from images, which are snapshots of the application and its dependencies, making it easy to distribute and replicate DB configurations. It allows streamlining development workflows, reducing configuration errors, and enhancing scalability and portability of DB environments.

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For the Application Layer and Presentation Layer connection, Docker ensures consistent environments across development, testing, and production. It simplifies dependency management by encapsulating all necessary dependencies within containers, enhancing security through isolation. Docker facilitates easy scaling and efficient resource utilization, supports seamless deployment, and integrates well with CI/CD pipelines.

Figure 34: The view of s.4 repository with Docker containers utilized by the service.

Currently, the developed application is dockerized using a structured approach, with each component encapsulated in its own Docker container for modularity and ease of deployment. The project consists of four primary repositories: 'ieq-tool' which provides a comprehensive Docker bundle for the entire application, 'ieq-frontend' which handles the user interface aspects, 'ieq-backend' which manages the server-side logic and API interactions, and 'ieq-postgres' which is responsible for the PostgreSQL DB configuration and management. This setup ensures that each part of the application can be developed, tested, and scaled independently, leveraging Docker's containerization technology to streamline development workflows and improve system reliability.

5.1.5.12. Presentation layer

The Presentation Layer is the last component of the service, responsible for delivering a UI that facilitates interaction between end-users and the underlying Application and Database layers. It serves as the face of the application, transforming complex backend processes and data into intuitive and interactive visualizations.

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The UI is built using React, a popular JavaScript library for building user interfaces, combined with TypeScript, a superset of JavaScript that adds static types. This combination leverages the strengths of both technologies, resulting in a robust, scalable, and maintainable codebase.

5.1.5.13. React

React is renowned for its component-based architecture, which promotes reusable and modular code. This approach allows developers to build complex UIs from small, isolated pieces of code called components.

- **Component-Based Architecture:** Each part of the UI is broken down into self-contained components. This modularity simplifies both development and maintenance.
- **Virtual DOM:** React uses a virtual DOM to optimize updates and rendering. This improves performance by minimizing direct manipulations to the actual DOM.
- **JSX:** React employs JSX, a syntax extension that allows HTML to be written within JavaScript. JSX enhances readability and ease of writing UI components.
- **State and Props:** React manages component state and props efficiently, enabling dynamic and interactive UIs. State holds data that may change over time, while props are used to pass data between components.

Name	Last commit	Last update
--		
public	scaffold	1 month ago
src	Added more components and endpoints	1 minute ago
.gitignore	scaffold	1 month ago
README.md	scaffold	1 month ago
package-lock.json	added the first router	2 weeks ago
package.json	added the first versin of a single chart	1 week ago
tailwind.config.js	scaffold	1 month ago
tsconfig.json	scale line component finished except css	2 weeks ago
yarn.lock	added the first versin of a single chart	1 week ago

Figure 35: The view of s.4 repository with React app 'main' folder.

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Name	Last commit	Last update
--		
components	Added more components and endpoints	just now
pages	added the first versin of a single chart	1 week ago
App.css	wip	1 week ago
App.test.tsx	scaffold	1 month ago
App.tsx	wip	1 week ago
index.css	scaffold	1 month ago
index.tsx	scaffold	1 month ago
logo.svg	scaffold	1 month ago
react-app-env.d.ts	scaffold	1 month ago
reportWebVitals.ts	scaffold	1 month ago
setupTests.ts	scaffold	1 month ago

Figure 36: The view of s.4 repository with React app 'src' folder.

5.1.5.14. TypeScript

TypeScript enhances JavaScript by adding static types, which catch errors at compile time rather than runtime. This ensures higher code quality and helps in maintaining large codebases.

- **Static Typing:** TypeScript introduces type annotations, providing compile-time checks to catch type-related errors early. This reduces runtime errors and improves code reliability.
- **Interfaces and Type Aliases:** These features enable the definition of complex types, improving the expressiveness and safety of the code. By defining interfaces and type aliases, developers can create clear contracts for components and functions.
- **Enhanced IDE Support:** TypeScript offers better code completion, navigation, and refactoring tools in modern IDEs, boosting developer productivity. Features like IntelliSense and autocompletion help developers write code more efficiently.
- **Compatibility with JavaScript:** TypeScript is fully compatible with JavaScript, allowing gradual adoption and integration with existing JavaScript code.

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```

1 {
2   "compilerOptions": {
3     "target": "es5",
4     "lib": [
5       "dom",
6       "dom.iterable",
7       "esnext",
8       "ES2023.Array"
9     ],
10    "allowJs": true,
11    "skipLibCheck": true,
12    "esModuleInterop": true,
13    "allowSyntheticDefaultImports": true,
14    "strict": true,
15    "forceConsistentCasingInFileNames": true,
16    "noFallthroughCasesInSwitch": true,
17    "module": "esnext",
18    "moduleResolution": "node",
19    "resolveJsonModule": true,
20    "isolatedModules": true,
21    "noEmit": true,
22    "jsx": "react-jsx"
23  },
24  "include": [
25    "src"
26  ]
27 }
28

```

Figure 37: The view of the 'tsconfig.json' file that states the use of TypeScript in s.4 React application.

5.1.5.15. User journey

The following example provides an indicative journey of the user through the service, starting from the home page of the application and moving to the next pages offering data analytics functionalities and providing relevant insights.

- The user chooses the room from the list of available rooms in each pilot.
- The 'Room Live View' section is the default opening screen after a room has been selected.
- The user selects an IEQ metric (e.g. temperature) and sensor of interest from the provided options as well as whether they would like to exclude anomalies from the analysis.
- An API request is sent to the corresponding endpoint, including the selected parameters.
- The API returns the latest data in JSON format, which is processed and displayed.

In a more abstract form, highlighting the main functionalities of the service, the workflow of s.4 can be summarized as follows:

- The user enters the service, getting an overview of the buildings rooms and sensors.
- Depending on the selected sensor(s), the user observes current IEQ variables, inspecting potential anomalies and bad practices, i.e. instances where IEQ was inadequate. Relevant evaluations based on global IEQ standards or building-specific constrains are also provided. Moreover, the user can inspect the feedback provided by the building occupants about IEQ, when available, and get insights about potential improvements.

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- In the second page, the user gets summary statistics and graphs to identify trends and patterns, thus receiving useful insights about the IEQ status, understanding potential issues, and identifying areas for improvement.
- In the third page, the user finds proposals about indicative measures that could be considered for improving the IEQ of the examined areas based on their special characteristics, use, and CH assets involved. These can include technical improvements but will mostly focus on soft measures like operational and behavioural changes.

5.2. Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management

5.2.1. Description

The aim of the service is to improve the energy management of CH buildings by providing accurate forecasts and data-driven recommendations. To achieve this goal, first, a set of forecasting models will be developed, tasked to accurately predict the energy consumed in particular areas of the buildings or in total, the indoor environmental conditions of the building areas, or special, intensive energy uses of the building (e.g. heating, cooling, lighting etc.) that energy management could focus on. This will include state-of-the-art ML models but also novel approaches, including Transfer Learning and Domain Adaptation, among others. In terms of optimization, intelligent energy management will focus on load shifting with the objective to reduce cost, shave peaks or exploit the benefits that energy production from RES and energy storage can offer. Advanced data analytics and reporting technics will further increase the value added by the service, equipping building energy managers with real-time insights that ensure optimized energy efficiency, indoor environmental quality, and thermal comfort. The service will be applied to pilot 1 (Croatia) and pilot 7 (Sweden) and replicated to pilot 3 (Greece).

5.2.2. Service Workflow

5.2.3. Input and Output Data

For this service, the input data are:

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Energy consumption (The data should illustrate for each building area and/or energy use of interest the energy consumed).

Energy management constraints (Information about the limitations present and other operational constraints that should be considered when shifting loads (e.g. hours of operation, thermal comfort)).

The output of the service may include one or more of the following:

- Forecasts for the following hours, days or weeks, summarizing the energy that is expected to be consumed per energy use, building area or in total.
- A schedule showing when flexible loads could operate based on the optimization criteria defined.

5.2.4. Internal Architecture

Similar to s.4, the service relies on REST API to manage core functionalities, such as parameter setting and fetching the desired data to provide analytical reports. The scripts are executed in Python. For data storage, PostgreSQL is used while data visualization, reports, and analytical representations are performed in the front-end using React. The connection between the Database Layer and the Application Layer adopts Docker as the core containerization technology. The architecture of the service is visualized below:

Figure 38: In-depth visualisation of s.5 architecture

5.2.5. Implementation

5.2.5.1. Database layer

The Database Layer employs PostgreSQL, which in this case is structured as follows:

1. **rooms_table**: This table contains information about each room, focusing on its location within the pilot buildings.
2. **reference_table**: Details the meters deployed in each room and/or electrical device, specifying the type of data collected by each sensor.
3. **history_table**: Stores meters readings along with timestamps. This allows for historical analysis of electricity consumption over time.
4. **working_hours_table**: Generated by the Application Layer, this table records the working hours associated with each pilot based on total energy consumption.
5. **forecasting_table**: Generated by the Application Layer, this table holds the output of forecasting models as reading them from the DB is much faster than running forecasting on the fly.
6. **optimization_table**: Generated by the Application Layer, this table stores the output of optimization algorithms that are based on the forecasting data and historical data since reading them from the DB is much faster than running forecasting live.

This structure enables comprehensive management and historical tracking of energy consumption data, supporting the optimization of the systems in terms for instance of energy cost, CO₂ emissions, or peak load, depending on the objectives at hand. For practical reasons, the data included in the BD can be grouped into three main categories based on their origin and purpose, namely Reference Mapping Data, Historical Sensor Data, and Generated Data, as described in the following sections.

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Figure 39: Visualisation of the s.5 DB schema

5.2.5.2. Reference Mapping Data

Within the s.5 architecture, the Reference Mapping Data category contains information that connects energy meters to specific rooms (stored in the 'reference_table') and maps rooms to their respective locations within each pilot project (managed through the 'rooms_table').

In the 'reference_table' in the DB schema, the primary key is the 'meter_id'. This table holds details about each meter, including its unique identifier, name, and the units of measurement. 'Device' and 'device_type' columns act as a reference to the specific electrical devices, if applied. This table includes 'room_id' as well, which links each meter with a room, if applicable.

The 'room_id' in the 'reference_table' acts as a foreign key (a relational DB constraint that ensures referential integrity by enforcing a link between tables based on a column's values), linking to entries in the 'rooms_table', and establishing a relationship between meters and their installation locations in rooms. The 'rooms_table' primarily details the spatial positions of rooms within the pilot building.

5.2.5.3. Historical Meters Data

The Historical Meters Data category comprises a single table, 'history_table', containing time series records of energy consumption captured by meters at regular intervals. This data is utilized for monitoring the energy consumed, training ML models, developing detection algorithms, and extracting insights.

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The primary key of the 'history_table' is composed of two columns: 'timestamp' (stored as 'datetime') and 'meter_id'. This composite key ensures that each record in the table is uniquely identified, allowing reliable referencing of each entry. 'Meter_id', linked to the 'reference_table', includes information about both the sensor and the specific metric being recorded.

5.2.5.4. Generated Data

The last category, Generated Data, consists of three tables, 'working_hours_table', 'optimization_table', 'forecasting_table'. They are created through interaction with Application Layer and are again used by the same layer in the analyses and forecast processes.

Working hours detection algorithm produces the 'working_hours_table' (this table is shared with s.4). It uses electricity consumption data to analyse user's behaviour and mark the hours when the building is occupied, allowing for analyses at hours when the building is actually occupied.

The 'forecasting_table' holds the output of the forecasting models. The forecasts are produced per 'meter_id', and for each meter the results are organized in a time series manner. This table is reused by the Application Layer as a part of the energy optimization algorithms and the output is saved back in the DB, under the name 'optimization_table'. It holds proposals to optimize shiftable loads in order to achieve energy efficiency.

5.2.5.5. Application layer

The Application Layer comprises a set of Python scripts that function as the backend of the service. This layer serves as an intermediary between the Database and presentation layers, with addition of framework to run the forecasting models, process and aggregate the results. The layer leverages REST API to handle data requests and responses, while SQL queries are performed through SQL Alchemy library to interact with and manipulate the DB.

In the following screenshot, the structure of the backend is presented:

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Figure 40: Visualisation of s.5 backend structure

The main components of the Application Layer are summarized below:

5.2.5.6. Database communication

This component includes the 'crud' folder and the 'models' folder, that are used to managing and structuring the DB contents.

The 'crud' folder contains functions dedicated to creating, reading, updating, and deleting (CRUD) operations on the DB. The 'models' folder defines the structure of each DB table. Both folders

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include three primary files, in addition to the `__init__.py` file: `'data.py'`, `'desc.py'`, and `'generated.py'`.

- **data.py**: Handles Historical Sensor data, ensuring accurate and efficient management of time-series information.
- **desc.py**: Manages Reference Mapping tables, crucial for defining relationships and mappings within the DB.
- **generated.py**: It is responsible for generated tables, such as the `'working_hours_table'`, `'forecasts_table'`, and `'optimizing_table'`, which are dynamically created as outputs of the models.

The functions within these folders utilize SQLAlchemy and the `'database.py'` file is used to establish a connection with the DB.

5.2.5.7. Data analysis

The second component includes the scripts that refer to patterns – mainly the `'room_patterns.py'` from folder `'routes'` that consist of endpoints connected through the REST API to the front-end. Also, some functions that are used in perform data aggregation, transformations, calculations and prepares the reported information (e.g. `'liveview_graphs.py'` and `'patters_graphs.py'`).

5.2.5.8. Forecasting

This component comprises scripts dedicated to forecasting models and functionalities. The scripts are designed to predict future trends and outcomes based on historical data, leveraging advanced ML algorithms.

The specific route, `'room_forecasts.py'` returns the result of `'forecasting_models.py'` scripts that implement the core ML algorithms for forecasting, utilizing historical data to predict future values and trends. It includes model training, validation, evaluation, and model-tuning processes to ensure accurate predictions.

5.2.5.9. Optimization algorithms

This component focuses on optimization techniques aimed at improving energy efficiency through advanced algorithms. The `'optimization_table'` is central to this category, holding the output from the `'proposal_functions.py'` and the route `'room_proposals.py'` returns the json-formatted output to be fetched by the UI.

5.2.5.10. Detection algorithms

The functions declared in `'detection_functions.py'` are designed to identify specific patterns of behavioural change, or anomalies within the data. These algorithms currently include working hours and anomaly detection mechanisms. The working hours detection algorithm identifies and

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records working hours in the 'working_hours_table' in the DB, while the anomaly detection is performed on the fly due to its quicker execution time, flagging irregularities that deviate from expected patterns. These detection functions enhance the application's capability to monitor and analyse data in an efficient manner.

5.2.5.11. REST API

The REST API is implemented using the FastAPI library, acting as the conduit between the backend processes and the frontend Presentation Layer. Since the primary purpose of the respective endpoints is to fetch and display data, GET requests are the most appropriate method.

Currently, the developed endpoints include:

Method	Endpoint	Description
Common Endpoints		
GET	/api/rooms/24/common/get_room_meters	Get Room Meters Api
GET	/api/rooms/24/common/get_all_meters	Get All Meters Api
GET	/api/rooms/24/common/get_all_rooms	Get All Rooms Api
Room Patterns		
GET	/api/rooms/24/patterns/graph_1	Graph 1 Api
GET	/api/rooms/24/patterns/graph_2	Graph 2 Api
Room Live View		
GET	/api/rooms/24/live-view/live-graph	Live Graph
GET	/api/rooms/24/live-view/stats	Get Statistics For Room
Room Forecasts		
GET	/api/rooms/24/forecast/main_graph	Room Forecasting
Room Proposals		
GET	/api/rooms/24/proposals/peak_identification	Room Peak Demand
GET	/api/rooms/24/proposals/action_endpoint	Room Proposed Action
GET	/api/rooms/24/proposals/optimization_graph	Room Optimization Graph
GET	/api/rooms/24/proposals/expected_improvements	Room Expected Improvements

Figure 41: Swagger of s.5 REST API

In the above screenshot, the endpoints are separated in 5 groups – Common endpoints return lists of meters, meters in specific room or rooms in the pilot building. Room Patterns perform data analysis based on historical data and user-set parameters. Room Live View returns the latest energy consumption graph data and latest room statistics related to energy consumption. The last two groups refer to data-driven intelligent management, Room Forecasts employ forecasting models to forecast energy consumption by meter, by room or for the whole building, while Room Proposals have a more complicated structure, separated by function. They include peak identification, return of proposed actions, visualization of optimization graph, and expected improvements in statistical form.

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For the endpoints mentioned above, different sets of parameters are required to produce specific results. For example, the endpoint that returns .json formatted data for the forecast graph visualization is as follows:

The image shows a Swagger UI interface for the endpoint `GET /api/rooms/24/forecast/main_graph`. The interface is titled "Room Forecasts" and includes a "Try it out" button. The parameters section lists four required query parameters:

- room_id**: Room ID (string, required). Input field contains "room_id".
- dropdown_et**: Energy type (string, required). Available values: Heating, AC, Water pump, EV charger. Input dropdown shows "Heating".
- dropdown_fw**: Time aggregation (string, required). Available values: End of Day, End of Week. Input dropdown shows "End of Day".
- dropdown_meter**: Meter (string, required). Available values: All, ac_24. Input dropdown shows "All".

The Responses section shows a 200 status code for a "Successful Response". The media type is set to `application/json`. An example JSON response is displayed in a dark box:

```

{
  "graph_output": {
    "additionalProp1": [
      {
        "Hour": 0,
        "value": 0
      }
    ],
    "additionalProp2": [
      {
        "Hour": 0,
        "value": 0
      }
    ],
    "additionalProp3": [
      {
        "Hour": 0,
        "value": 0
      }
    ]
  }
}

```

Figure 42: Swagger of s.5 REST API – Room Forecast Graph

In the picture above the first section of the endpoint refers to the parameters that will be set by user. In this case, user will have to choose the desired energy type (by energy device), meter (or keep 'All' that is the default value), and desired time aggregation. Additionally, 'room_id' will be set automatically from the UI.

5.2.5.12. Docker

As done in s.4, Docker is used to automate the deployment of applications inside lightweight, portable containers, encapsulating an application and its dependencies.

5.2.5.13. Presentation layer

The Presentation Layer is the last component of the service, responsible for delivering a UI that facilitates interaction between end-users and the underlying Application and Database Layers. It serves as the face of the application, transforming complex backend processes and data into intuitive and interactive visualizations. The UI is built using React, combined with TypeScript, using the same technology and logic as s.4.

The following example provides an indicative journey of the user through the service, starting from the home page of the application and moving to the next pages offering data analytics and forecasting functionalities and providing relevant insights in terms of energy management.

- The user chooses the room from the list of available rooms in each pilot.
- The "Room Live View" section is the default opening screen after room selection.
- The user selects a desired type of energy to visualize (e.g. AC, Heating) and meter from the provided options, as well as whether they would like to exclude anomalies.
- An API request is sent to the corresponding endpoint, including the selected parameters.
- The API returns the latest data in JSON format, which is processed and displayed.

In a more abstract form, highlighting the main functionalities of the service, the workflow of s.5 can be summarized as follows:

- The user enters the service, getting an overview of the building rooms and sensors.
- Based on the selected sensor(s), the user observes in relevant graphs the actual energy currently consumed by the building at different levels (e.g. in total or per room) as well as the day/week-ahead forecasts provided by the models.
- On the second page, the user can get summary statistics and graphs to identify trends and patterns, thus receiving insights about the energy consumed and proposals for potential improvements.
- On the last page, the user can inspect a schedule, indicating when each of the shiftable loads should operate based on the optimization criteria defined.

5.3. Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real time monitoring and management

5.3.1. Description

The digital twin to be developed in INHERIT is a virtual replica of the cultural heritage building and is used to provide meaningful information about the CH operation & management (energy & comfort) to building users and maintenance managers.

The CH digital twin includes:

1. Static data of the CH and its systems included in the BIM models.
2. Dynamic data of the CH provided by the monitoring systems.

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3. Data processing providing indicators and scores of CH and users performance.
4. Energy performance models allowing to simulate scenarios and carry out what-if analysis about potential conservation measures.

The DT system will enable:

1. Remote inspection and visualization of BIM models as well as real-time and historical data on energy and indoor environment quality
2. Energy efficiency and indoor environment quality evaluation and monitoring
3. Generation and visualization of energy & IEQ performance deviation alarms
4. Automatic sensors incidences detection
5. Identify areas for improvement and quantifying savings potential based on an optimally operated and maintained reference CH
6. Enable simulation scenarios and what-if analysis to evaluate impact of behavioural changes or conservation measures with high accuracy
7. Support preventive maintenance
8. Visualize all data and calculations in the DT graphical interface which is divided into a 3D visualization (BIM based) and a navigation/control panel

5.3.2. Service Workflow

5.3.3. Input & Output Data

Input data of INHERIT's DT:

DS1- Static CH data. The DT enables to visualize all the static data included in the BIM model of the CH. The information will be collected through the BIM model file (it can be an ifc file, a rvt file, etc.). The information that should be included in the BIM file is:

- General information: Location, address
- Geometry: spaces distribution
- Envelope materials: walls, roofs, ceilings, floors
- Lighting system: location, geometry, type, power (W)
- Other equipment: PCs, printers, elevators
- HVAC system: production, distribution and terminal units elements and features

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DS2- Dynamic monitoring data on CH performance. The DT collects, visualize and exploits real time data on building performance. There are several means for data collection. The DT system can connect to the monitoring system or BACS in the CH building using MQTT, API, etc. We can discuss the situation for every pilot. The data set size depends on the pilot size and monitoring level. It is recommended to collect data every 5 minutes. The data collected for the first pillar (energy and comfort) is:

- Energy consumption: monitored both at building level and room level by type of consumption (total, lighting, air conditioning, other equipment).
- Outdoor environment: the system should monitor outdoor temperature, humidity, and solar radiation in the location of the CH.
- Indoor environment: temperature, humidity and CO2 should be measured for each room while others variables such as lighting level could be also measured depending on the pilot

DS3 – Energy and IEQ performance models to calculate scores and carry out what-if analysis. The BEM models are developed with python & energy plus files (.py, .idf)

Output data for INHERIT's DT:

- Visualization of real-time and historical energy and indoor environment quality monitoring data in the BIM model and navigation panel (values & heatmaps displays in the BIM model; graphs display in the navigation/control panel)
2. Energy and IEQ alarms displayed in the BIM models and navigation/control panel (e.g. lights were on last night in room XX, you have wasted X €)
 3. Energy and IEQ dynamic scores displayed in the BIM model (values & heat maps) and the navigation/control panel (graphs)
 4. Reference optimally operated and maintained CH building consumption (kWh) displayed in the navigation/control panel and compared to the real CH building (graphs)
 5. Energy consumption savings (kWh, €, %, etc.) corresponding to a potential conservation measure or scenario displayed in the navigation/control panel (graphs)

5.3.4. Internal Architecture

Figure 43: Digital Twin Architecture

Figure 43 shows a detailed overview of the architecture and technologies used in the digital twin service. The technologies used are:

Kubernetes: is an open-source platform designed to automate deploying, scaling, and operating application containers. It will facilitate the orchestration of our entire application and microservices.

Python: is a high-level, interpreted programming language known for its simplicity and readability. It is used due to its ease of use, extensive libraries and frameworks that can accelerate the development of microservices, data analysis and manipulation. Its simplicity accelerates development and reduces the probability of errors.

PWA: A Progressive Web App is a type of application software delivered through the web, designed to work on any platform that uses a standards-compliant browser. PWAs can work offline, load quickly, and provide a native app-like experience. This is crucial for users who need to access the application without a constant internet connection.

React: is a JavaScript library for building user interfaces. React allows us to build dynamic and responsive user interfaces efficiently. Its component-based architecture promotes reusability and easier management of the UI, making development faster and more maintainable.

IndexedDB: is a low-level API for client-side storage of significant amounts of structured data, including files/blobs. IndexedDB is used to store data locally in the browser, allowing the application to function offline and synchronize with the server when connectivity is restored.

MongoDB: is a NoSQL database that stores data in flexible, JSON-like documents. It is designed to handle unstructured data efficiently. MongoDB is used in OpenDBL for its ability to handle unstructured data, such as forms, efficiently. Its schema-less design allows for rapid iteration and flexibility in data modelling, which is beneficial for our application's evolving requirements.

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PostgreSQL: It is a powerful, open source object-relational database system that uses and extends the SQL language combined with many features that safely store and scale the most complicated data workloads. PostgreSQL comes with many features aimed to help developers build applications, administrators to protect data integrity and build fault-tolerant environments, and help you manage your data no matter how big or small the dataset. In addition to being free and open source, PostgreSQL is highly extensible

Kafka: Apache Kafka (Kafka) is an open-source, distributed streaming platform that enables (among other things) the development of real-time, event-driven applications and user experiences on the web. It enables to build applications that continuously consume and process these streams at extremely high speeds, with a high level of fidelity and accuracy based on the correct order of their occurrence.

Autodesk: The Autodesk Platform Service is used for the visualization, edition, processing and management of BIM models. This is Autodesk's cloud development platform which is a set of web service APIs. In this case, Data Management API and Model derivative API will be used.

Energyplus: EnergyPlus is the calculation engine used in the digital twin. It is a building energy simulation program for modelling the energy consumption of heating, cooling, ventilation, lighting and other electrical equipment as well as water use. EnergyPlus is a terminal program that reads inputs and writes outputs to text files.

Figure 44: Digital Twin Architecture & technologies

5.3.5. Implementation

The digital twin architecture has following layers:

The Storage Layer

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This layer comprises both NoSQL and SQL databases to store diverse types of data. NoSQL databases are utilized for storing unstructured or semi-structured data, providing flexibility, scalability and good performance working with IoT data. While SQL databases are used for structured data that require complex queries and structured data. This dual-database approach ensures efficient handling of varied data types, enhancing the system's overall performance and reliability.

The Messaging Orchestrator Layer

This layer includes a messaging orchestrator that handles communication between IoT sensors and other components of the system. It manages the flow of data from various IoT sensors to the appropriate microservices and/or databases, ensuring efficient and reliable data transmission. This orchestrator plays a crucial role in maintaining the system's responsiveness and real-time capabilities.

The Microservices Layer

In this layer, microservices are implemented to manage different aspects of the application. Each microservice is responsible for specific tasks, such as alert notification services or other specialized processes (data analysis, data transform, etc). This architecture supports high modularity and scalability, allowing individual services to be developed, deployed, and scaled independently. This flexibility ensures the system can adapt and grow according to future requirements.

The Frontend Layer

This layer is responsible for the user interface and user experience. It includes a front-end application that interacts with the API to display data and provide functionalities to the users. Additionally, there is a 3D viewer component that enables visualization data in a three-dimensional format. This layer ensures that users have an interactive and engaging interface for accessing the application's features.

5.4. Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns

5.4.1. Description

Crowd monitoring has become a vital aspect of managing public spaces, especially given the increasing frequency of mass gatherings at concerts, sporting events, and public demonstrations. Technological advancements have empowered security, safety, and event management professionals to efficiently monitor and respond to crowd behaviours, whether in ensuring safe movement or identifying potential security threats. Applications fall broadly into two main categories: vision-based systems that rely on cameras and sensors, and non-vision-based systems that use a variety of wireless technologies to capture crowd data. Understanding the different approaches and methods used in these applications is crucial for balancing public safety and privacy concerns.

By using a diverse range of sensors and sophisticated analytical techniques, crowd monitoring systems are increasingly capable of ensuring safety, detecting threats, and facilitating efficient crowd management.

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In conclusion, crowd monitoring applications provide essential tools for enhancing public safety and optimizing the management of large gatherings. The integration of various sensors and analytical techniques is fundamental to striking a balance between comprehensive monitoring and addressing the technical and ethical challenges involved.

In the context of [INHERIT project](#), SLG will implement a service that will collect data from sensors to estimate the number of people in different rooms in the given building. The ultimate goal of the service is to provide insights on the mobility patterns of occupants and assist facility managers with crowd management considering 2 main use cases: i) support of evacuation strategies; ii) optimize user comfort through better management of rooms by analysing Indoor Environment Quality (IEQ) and people's presence in the rooms.

During the initial phase of the project, the key requirements that have been identified are summarized below:

- FR7.1 The system should gather data related to people's presence, analyze them and provide insights.
- FR7.5, Trigger alarms for facility managers when spaces are over occupied
- FR7.3, The system should analyze the mobility data with thermal comfort to identify correlations and optimize comfort and efficiency

5.4.2. Service Workflow

The service for crowd monitoring and optimization will follow a structured five-step process. Initially, sensors will be strategically placed throughout the pilot premises to collect data on visitor movement and other relevant behavioral parameters. The data will then be transmitted to a centralized system, where it will be preprocessed and analyzed to extract meaningful insights, which include visualizations like visitor heatmaps and traffic flow analyses, and will subsequently support operational decision-making. Pilot administrators will then be able to use these insights to optimize exhibit placement, signage, and staff deployment. Furthermore, the service operates in real-time, continuously monitoring visitor activity, and generating alerts for immediate action in case of anomalies or significant deviations, ensuring efficient and adaptive management of the pilot environment.

5.4.3. Input and Output Data

The implemented service will collect as input real-time data from various sensors placed across different places and rooms of a building. These sensors will measure:

- Occupancy data (number of people present in the building and potentially in each room).
- Movement data to track mobility patterns across different areas.
- Indoor Environment Quality metrics such as temperature, humidity, and air quality.

The process of the acquired input from the sensors will provide an output the following:

- Occupancy levels of the building and its rooms, relative to each room's estimated proper capacity.
- Alerts when room occupancy exceeds safety thresholds or IEQ deteriorates beyond acceptable levels.
- Visual representations of crowd mobility patterns, such as heatmaps and traffic flow analysis.

5.4.4. Internal Architecture

The system is designed around a distributed architecture with the following components:

Strategic Sensing and Data Relay Layer: Infrared and environmental sensors installed in strategic locations to collect real-time occupancy and IEQ data. Sensors transmit data wirelessly to a centralized processing unit, either through Wi-Fi or other communication protocols (e.g., LoRa or Zigbee for low-power devices).

Processing Layer: The data is first preprocessed to filter noise and ensure accuracy. Advanced algorithms then analyze mobility patterns and IEQ correlations to provide actionable insights. This layer also handles real-time alert generation for safety and comfort.

Visualization Layer: Data is fed into a user interface, providing real-time visualizations such as top-view building layouts with occupancy metrics, IEQ heatmaps, and traffic flow diagrams. Alerts and suggestions are presented to building administrators when thresholds are breached.

Figure 45: Internal Architecture for Real-time Insights service

5.4.5. Implementation

The implementation phase is currently in progress:

Sensor Selection: A preliminary overview (Table 5) has identified infrared sensors as the primary option for tracking room occupancy due to their reliability and non-intrusiveness.

Data Collection Infrastructure: The architecture for gathering and transmitting sensor data has been outlined, and the sensor network is being tested in initial pilots.

Analytics Development: Basic algorithms for occupancy tracking and IEQ monitoring are being developed, with further enhancements planned to integrate real-time decision support features like evacuation assistance and room optimization.

User Interface: A prototype UI is under development, focusing on clear visual representations of occupancy and IEQ data. Continuous monitoring features and alert systems are being tested for responsiveness and accuracy.

Future Plans: The next phase will involve refining data analysis capabilities, further integration of IEQ data, and testing the system in real-world scenarios to ensure scalability and accuracy.

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Table 6: Analysis of Hardware that could be used for Real-time insights service

Equipment	Description	Price Range	Pros	Cons	Comments	Usage Example
Infrared (IR) sensors	Detect presence by measuring infrared light emitted by bodies.	\$2 - \$50	Cost-effective, simple to install	Limited range, affected by environmental factors	Limited range, affected by environmental factors	Used at entry and exit points to count the number of visitors entering and leaving the building, providing data on visitor flow.
Ultrasonic sensors	Use ultrasonic waves to detect movement and presence.	\$20 - \$100	Larger coverage area, not affected by lighting	Can be affected by temperature and humidity	Can be affected by temperature and humidity	Placed in large open spaces like galleries to monitor the number of visitors and their movement patterns.
Passive Infrared (PIR) sensors	Detect motion within a specific range using infrared.	\$10 - \$30	Inexpensive, low power consumption	Limited detection range, false positives in hot environments	Limited detection range, false positives in hot environments	Installed in hallways to detect visitor movement, ensuring areas are monitored for occupancy without continuous video surveillance.
LiDAR Sensors	Create 3D maps using laser beams for accurate detection.	\$300 - \$2000+	-High accuracy, detailed mapping	High cost, complex installation	High cost, complex installation	Placed in exhibition areas to create accurate 3D maps of visitor movements and detect crowding in specific exhibits.
Time-of-Flight (ToF) Sensors	Measure light travel time to create depth maps.	\$100 - \$500	Accurate depth measurement, good range	Can be expensive, requires calibration	Can be expensive, requires calibration	Used in entrance halls and large rooms to map out visitor flow and monitor crowd density in real-time.

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RFID Tags	Track individual movements via wearable tags.	\$1 - \$10 per tag, \$500 for readers	Accurate -real-time data for	tracking, Requires distribution, concerns	tag Requires privacy concerns	tag Visitors are given RFID tags upon entry, allowing for real-time tracking of their location and movement throughout the building.
Bluetooth Beacons	Interact with mobile devices for location data.	\$5 - \$30 per beacon	Leverages devices, effective	visitors' cost-usage, privacy issues	smartphone potential Requires smartphone potential issues	Beacons are placed at key points to interact with visitors' smartphones, providing data on their location and movement within the building.
Wi-Fi Analytics	Analyze signals from smartphones to monitor movement.	Varies widely, typically subscription-based	Uses infrastructure, time data	existing real-device privacy concerns	Depends on visitor connection, privacy concerns	Depends on visitor device connection, privacy concerns Utilizes the building's Wi-Fi network to analyze the movement patterns and density of visitors based on their smartphone signals.

6. Preservation & maintenance' services

The preservation and maintenance services focused on cultural heritage buildings include the Preventive Maintenance with H-BIM, a GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance, and Heritage Buildings Environmental Climate Scenarios. The H-BIM service will create a collaborative, multidimensional model to analyse various renovation scenarios, ensuring compliance with energy performance and interoperability standards. The GIS-based solution will leverage AI to classify and digitally map CH buildings, guiding stakeholders in optimal maintenance planning. Additionally, the Climate Scenarios service will assess the impacts of climate hazards on CH buildings, using Copernicus data to calculate relevant KPIs, this promoting sustainability and resilience in heritage conservation.

6.1. Preventive Maintenance with H-BIM

6.1.1. Description

INHERIT Service 8 will propose an implementation method to integrate all the information collected during the Technical Inspection (Task 3.1) into an H-BIM model. Defining and explaining all the development phases of the methodology is fundamental to understand the procedures and to obtain a useful and efficient model that aims to solve all the current Cultural Heritage needs.

This service pretends:

- **Collection, digitisation, and management of CH building information.** Obtain a useful methodology to ensure a comprehensive and efficient management of buildings and help decision-makers.
- **Improve conservation and maintenance of CH.** Use innovative procedures to ensure its artistic, cultural, and historic value. To build a global scenario with all the relevant information about the current status of the building, its construction systems, and materials characteristics.
- **Optimisation of operations.** Improve efficiency and cost-effectiveness of future planning of any intervention through the analysis of different scenarios and data interoperability.

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Figure 46: Preliminary intentions of the Preventive Maintenance methodology with H-BIM

6.1.2. Service Workflow

To draw this service, different development stages will be carried out, the first of them being data collection. This phase will be mandatory to properly build the 3D model and also to obtain fundamental data on the current state of conservation of the CH building, such as existing pathologies, past interventions, current needs, and the main technical and historical characteristics that may be useful for its maintenance and conservation, such as the materials or construction systems used.

The information will be collected by applying INHERIT's Technical Inspection methodology as well as consulting existing documentation (layouts, past intervention projects, historical archive documents...) and must be reliable, accessible and useful for those responsible for managing and

maintaining the heritage. Once all existing information on the CH asset has been obtained, the definition and planning of the H-BIM project should be carried out.

6.1.3. Input & Output Data

The H-BIM model that will serve as the basis for developing the preventive maintenance service will be fed with different types of information about the building that will allow users to know its technical characteristics, its needs, and its state of conservation (Ladiana & Sivo, 2019). This model will be designed to integrate and manage multidimensional building data, which is fundamental for informed decision-making and the creation of a Digital Twin.

An approach based on the integration of information provides a robust platform for proactive and sustainable conservation, enabling service users to anticipate potential problems and plan appropriate solutions that respect the integrity of the CH.

Some of the most characteristic information to be collected on the pilot that will demonstrate the service are:

Figure 47: Input information for building the HBIM model for Preventive Maintenance of Heritage Buildings

1. Geometric Model:

This type of information includes the precise dimensions of the building, its shape, and structure. It is essential for constructing an accurate digital representation of the building that will allow for the visualization and analysis of the current physical state of the heritage asset.

2. Construction Stage:

Data related to the phases of the building's construction, including techniques and materials used at different points in its history. This information is crucial for understanding the building's evolution and the potential implications for its conservation and maintenance.

3. Thermal Behaviour:

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This refers to how the building interacts with its environment in terms of energy, insulation, and thermal efficiency. Understanding thermal behaviour is vital for planning interventions that improve energy sustainability without compromising the heritage value.

4. Facilities:

This includes the building's mechanical, electrical and plumbing. Documenting the facilities is essential for managing their maintenance and planning future renovations or interventions effectively.

5. Monitoring Data:

This category covers the collection of periodic or real-time data on the building's condition, such as sensors monitoring humidity, temperature, or structural movement. Monitoring data allows for the detection of emerging issues and the evaluation of the effectiveness of preventive maintenance actions. However, in heritage buildings it is not always possible to install sensors due to their characteristics or the level of protection of the assets.

6. Pathologies:

The identification and documentation of pathologies, or structural and material problems within the building, is essential for determining areas that require immediate intervention. This includes damage caused by aging, weathering, or previous interventions.

7. Building Systems:

This involves documenting the construction methods and technologies employed in the building. Understanding the original construction systems and those applied in subsequent renovations is fundamental for planning any conservation or intervention work.

8. Material Characteristics:

Detailed information about the materials used, such as their composition, origin, and behaviour over time. This information is important for selecting restoration materials that are compatible with the originals and ensuring the building's durability.

9. Historical Information:

Historical data that provides context on the cultural, social, and architectural value of the building. This information is essential for making decisions that respect the historical integrity of the heritage asset.

10. Maintenance, Renovation, and Intervention Actions:

A record of all previous and planned actions in terms of maintenance, renovation, and other interventions. This history is key to designing a coherent preventive maintenance plan.

6.1.3.1. Data gathering

To achieve a reliable model, it is essential to have adequate information about the pilot. The quality of the data and the quantity or difficulty in obtaining it will be fundamental in assessing the reliability of the H-BIM model and the feasibility of implementing the methodology.

Some of the most relevant limitations on this issue could be:

1. **Access to the CH site & quality of existing documentation**
 - Many heritage buildings may have limited access to protect their structural integrity or because of their current use.
 - Older buildings can be structurally fragile making inspection risky for workers and their integrity.
2. **Technological Challenges & Technical Expertise**
 - Heritage structures often are unique, and their geometry is complex to model, so the use of parametric family elements can be difficult.
 - Specialised skills are required to work on Heritage BIM projects
3. **Regulatory & Compliance Issues**
 - CH buildings may have higher protection standards that make it difficult to carry out any intervention or deployment of real-time monitoring.
 - Projects may require approval from multiple stakeholders and must comply with preservation laws.
4. **Resource Intensity**
 - Data gathering and modelling cost and time in CH buildings may be more expensive due to the above limitations

These limitations in data collection can significantly affect the project's progress and outcomes. Therefore, it is important to take them into account during the planning of the service development.

6.1.4. Internal Architecture

Carry out of Service 8 should offer a comprehensive framework for a properly conservation and management of CH buildings with H-BIM.

It is necessary to explain that this service will develop a methodology using Autodesk Revit (BIM software), it is not an ICT service (no software development required).

After reviewing the current literature, a diagram of the architecture of the service is shown below (Nieto et al., 2016):

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Figure 48: H-BIM architecture for Preventive Maintenance

The H-BIM-based preventive maintenance service architecture can be broken down into several functional layers, integrating different tools and workflows:

1. Information Model Layer (Information Model Layer)
 - Collected Data: Historical documents, photos, point cloud data, as-built drawings, and technical reports.
 - Data Processing: Generation of parametric and geometric 3D models.
2. Integration Layer
 - Data Fusion: Integration of semantic information and technical inspection data into a cohesive model.
3. Application Layer
 - Analysis and Management: Application of the processed information for documentation, conservation planning, and risk management.
4. Final Output
 - Digital Twin (Service 6): Creation of a digital twin of the heritage building to facilitate preventive maintenance and conservation.

6.1.5. Implementation

The following diagram shows the workflow of the service emphasising the different stages of development of the H-BIM methodology and the relationship between them (Giuliani et al., 2024).

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Figure 49: Workflow of H-BIM Project Development for Preventive Maintenance Methodology

The H-BIM model-building process starts with data gathering, which consists of on-site Laser Scanning and image capture to obtain an initial point cloud to derive a surface mesh model with texture and colour information (Photorealistic 3D model). These elements together with the collected information will also be used to build a library with parametric objects that will result into an H-BIM project.

The workflow of the H-BIM project is divided into inspection (Information derived from the Technical Inspection), documentation, and data management involving identification and labelling of pieces, association of construction systems as well as inventory and criteria for the management of building elements.

6.1.5.1. Heritage Building Information Modeling (H-BIM)

The goal to be achieved by developing this service is to get an innovative methodology that links the BIM approach with the cultural value of heritage buildings and their preventive maintenance (Khan et al., 2022).

The results obtained from the intersection of these three concepts are explained below.

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Figure 50: Potential consequences of the intersections between BIM Methodology, Conservation of Heritage Buildings and Preventive Maintenance

- **BIM methodology** focuses on control and management, integration of information, and interoperability.
- The **conservation and enhancement of Cultural Heritage** is supported by research and documentation based on its cultural, artistic, and historical value.
- **Preventive Maintenance** is carried out through technical inspections, risk assessments, and monitoring.

The intersection of the three concepts aims at an innovative methodology that promotes multidisciplinary collaboration, digitalisation of CH with integrated data for predictive analytics, and optimisation of planning and costs of conservation and reuse of buildings with continuous updating of the maintenance status of buildings for proactive and sustainable conservation of CH.

6.2. GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance

6.2.1. Description

The aim of the service is to guide heritage managers, engineers, architects, and building operators to identify proper maintenance plans for CH buildings based on their particular characteristics and similarities. To achieve this goal, the service provides a GIS-based interface that visualizes CH buildings in an interactive map and summarizes key information about the architectural style and design of the building, its overall condition, and the CH assets involved. Moreover, by exploiting advanced image processing models, the service clusters CH buildings into categories based on

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their similarity. The service will be applied to pilot 3 (Greece) and pilot 7 (Sweden) and replicated to pilot 4 (Latvia).

6.2.2. Service Workflow

6.2.3. Internal Architecture

Figure 51: In-depth visualisation of the GIS-based service architecture

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In the diagram above, the main components of the service and their interactions are visualized. In general, its structure can be described as follows: the Database Layer is responsible for storing the data in two forms – text type data that resembles the data labeling of the images and the images itself; the Algorithm Layer orchestrates the data base and user interface connection, as well as hosting the image processing models – pre-trained AI image recognition model and models responsible for image clustering; the Presentation Layer represents the user interface starting from user authorization and following to GIS-based interface that visualizes the outputs of Algorithm Layer’s image processing models – interactive map with buildings and clustering statistics.

In a more abstract form, highlighting the main functionalities of the service, the workflow of s.9 can be summarized as follows:

- The user enters the service and accesses a map where the broader area of the pilot is presented, and the CH buildings are displayed. By clicking on the buildings, the user can obtain information about their special characteristics.
- On another page, the user observes the clusters constructed and the features that contributed most to their categorizations. This includes summary statistics about the examined buildings, both static and graphical. Based on the above, renovation and maintenance actions that have performed well in certain CH buildings can be recommended for other CH buildings of similar characteristics.

6.2.4. Input & Output Data

The input data of the service may include the following:

Building characteristics (Key, static information about the CH buildings to be analysed, including their position, ownership, architecture style, design, and year of construction)

Building images (Images of CH buildings within the broader area of the pilot that can help analyse their design, condition, and particularities)

The output data of the service may include the following:

1. An interactive map, presenting the CH buildings within the examined area. The user will be able to inspect the buildings by reviewing key information related to their style, design, and image.
2. A list, showing the constructed classes and the buildings included in each category, along with features that contributed most to said categorization.

6.2.5. Implementation

6.2.5.1. Database Layer

The database layer is hosted on PostgreSQL. In this specific case, the data includes a set of images, that will be stored externally. While PostgreSQL offers the technical capabilities to store images as binary data, it may lead to slower response speed, longer waiting time and overall worse degree of optimization. However, the stored images are linked to the application and database through data labeling.

6.2.5.2. Data labeling

The set of CH building images is described in detail covering the main aspects of building managers' interest – number of stores, size of windows, heating system, energy efficiency class and building materials for the specific parts of the building. The mentioned labels may be added or removed in the sense that the AI system is not hardcoded to take into account these features.

6.2.5.3. CH Buildings images

Among with the stored CH building images, the street view of the neighbouring heritage buildings has to be analyzed. Cities (especially in the Southern Europe) are often built in clusters-neighbourhoods during one epoch. That allows the identification of similar features (e.g. architectural styles, design items, building materials) and possible issues that may emerge from said features (e.g. heat loss through wooden windows during winter).

6.2.5.4. Street View images

The street view data is acquired through open-source mapping resources (e.g. Mapillary.com) and there is a possibility of their supplementation from locally stored photos of the neighbouring streets with added geolocation.

6.2.5.5. Algorithm output

The output of the Algorithm layer can potentially be too big to be performed ad-hoc. It is much more efficient for it to be stored in the database and to simply be requested every time the application is used. For each of the two main parts of the service (GIS-based interactive map and clustering visualization), a separate table is created by the Algorithm layer to be used in future queries.

6.2.5.6. Algorithm Layer

The Algorithm Layer is focused on performing calculations for the Presentation Layer using the Database Layer. It includes the most essential part of the service - pre-trained AI models and clustering models used to analyze images of the CH buildings - and is executed using the Python programming language.

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The final part of the Algorithm Layer is the Image Processing Models and it consists of AI pretrained models and Clustering methods. For both cases, open-source models or the combination of such will be used. As far as the output of the Algorithm Layer will be stored in the Database Layer and, therefore, a long ad-hoc running time is out not an issue, there is freedom to run and experiment with a number of models. As such, different methods will run and compete every time the data set is renewed.

6.2.5.7. Database communication

Firstly, one of the components of this layer refers to data base communication, which is performed with the SQLAlchemy package. One of the key features of SQLAlchemy is its ORM, which maps Python classes to database tables and instances of those classes to rows in the corresponding tables. This means that using Python the Algorithm Layer is able to manipulate objects and methods to perform CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) operations on the Database Layer.

6.2.5.8. Data pre-processing

Next integral part is data pre-processing – prior to using AI and clustering models, some aspects of the data have to be analyzed and clarified. The input images undergo preprocessing to ensure it is in the correct format and resolution for the VLM. This may include resizing, normalization, and conversion to a suitable format (e.g., JPEG, PNG). Preprocessing helps in standardizing the input data and improving the performance of the model. Next, features from existing data labels are extracted and mapped with the matching images.

6.2.5.9. Pre-trained AI image recognition models

The architectural features of a building play a crucial role in assisting building managers and occupants in achieving energy efficiency, sustainability, and preservation of CH buildings. Unfortunately, developing an accurate DL model requires a substantial amount of labeled training data, energy, and time. Recently emerged, sophisticated pre-trained vision-language models (VLMs) like GPT-4 Vision, LLaVa 1.5, and BakLLaVa can offer a solution.

These pre-trained AI image recognition models are advanced ML algorithms that have been trained on vast data sets to recognize and classify objects, patterns, and features within images. For this service, open-source AI models will be fine-tuned in the background every time the database changes or gets enriched. They will compete on a validation set consisting of several CH images that will be treated as “ground-truth”. The model with the highest success ratio will be presented to the user.

The DL models have been initially trained on vast datasets, such as ImageNet, which contain millions of labeled images across thousands of categories. During training, the model learns to recognize various features at different levels of abstraction, from simple edges and textures to complex patterns and objects.

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Vision-Language Models (VLMs) are advanced artificial intelligence systems designed to understand and process both visual and textual information simultaneously (also known as Dual-Stream Architecture).

1. The visual encoder is responsible for processing images. It usually consists of region-based convolutional neural networks (R-CNNs) that extract the features from the input images. These features capture details such as shapes, textures, and objects present in the images.

When an image is fed into the model, it gets broken into sectors and each sector passes through multiple layers R-CNN to have its features extracted. Each layer extracts progressively higher-level features. For example, the initial layers might detect edges and textures, while deeper layers might recognize more complex structures like windows, doors, or architectural styles. In the end, each image is assigned with probabilities to belong (or to possess) to a certain class (or keyword/feature).

The flow of the R-CNN analysis of the VLMs is described in a scheme below:

Figure 52: Overview of the R-CNN architecture

2. The language encoder processes textual data. It often uses transformer-based architectures, such as BERT or GPT, to encode the text into a sequence of contextualized embeddings. These embeddings capture the semantic meaning and context of the text. These prompts are sent automatically from the Algorithm Layer to receive a required description.
3. The key component of VLMs is the cross-modal interaction layer, which fuses the visual and textual information. This layer allows the model to align and correlate features from both modalities, enabling it to understand how the visual content relates to the textual content.

For the optimal training of the AI model, fine tuning is required. During this process, we ensure that the service-specific features, mentioned in the Database Layer – Data labeling, are included in the model. So, for a limited number of CH buildings' photos, labeling will be performed by the developers of the service and will focus on most visible and most impactful architectural features. After being fine-tuned on a smaller, CH building images dataset, the AI model will have access to the street view images. This set of images is much larger, acquired automatically with addition of locally stored images and has geolocation available. The last part is essential for final Presentation Layer map screen.

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Overall, the data flow of this part of the Algorithm Layer can be visualized in the scheme below:

Figure 53: In-depth visualisation of the R-CNN architecture

The output can be presented both as list of keywords, used in future clustering and analysis, and in user-friendly text form, that could be displayed when clicking on specific buildings. It is saved back in the database, to avoid long waiting times when calling it from endpoints.

6.2.5.10. Clustering models

The features extracted by the model can be used as input to clustering models. These models group similar buildings based on the extracted features, enabling the identification of maintenance plans that have been effective for buildings with similar characteristics.

Clustering relies on a similarity measure to determine how closely related data points are. Common similarity measures include Euclidean distance, cosine similarity, and Manhattan distance. The choice of similarity measure depends on the nature of the data and the specific clustering algorithm used.

There are a number of common clustering algorithms that are going to be used: K-means, Hierarchical Clustering, DBSCAN, GMM. Similar to AI models, each time the database is refreshed, the clustering algorithm will determine the best model for that specific set of datapoints.

Clustering allows grouping similar CH buildings based on their architectural features, materials, condition, and other relevant attributes. This helps in identifying common problems and possible renovations / optimizations that will compile in a targeted maintenance plans that are more likely to be effective for buildings with similar features.

An indicative example of the above mechanic is displayed below:

6.2.5.11. Presentation Layer

The Presentation Layer of your GIS-based service stands as the interactive gateway for users, seamlessly integrating advanced analytics with an intuitive user experience. This layer is designed to offer a dynamic and user-friendly interface, with secure user authorization mechanisms to ensure data privacy and access control. Besides the authentication screen, it consists of two main screens - the interactive map used to access information about individual building profiles, architectural styles, design elements, and overall condition; and the visualization of the constructed clusters with summary statistics. This enables users to make informed decisions by recommending tailored renovation and maintenance strategies based on the specific characteristics and similarities of each building cluster.

6.2.5.12. User authentication

Each pilot will have a separated database and, therefore, the users of one pilot will be able to connect to the database of that specific pilot only. This approach ensures data security and privacy while also allowing for tailored analysis and maintenance strategies specific to the cultural and architectural nuances of each pilot area. Modular services can handle large datasets more efficiently, ensuring that the clustering and image processing models are optimized for each pilot.

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6.2.5.13. CH buildings interactive map

Upon logging in, users are presented with a comprehensive GIS-based interface that serves as a digital gateway to the CH landscape of their designated pilot area. The interactive map offers a panoramic view of the broader region, with marked and categorized CH buildings. Clicking on individual buildings reveals the architectural and historical characteristics of the selected building, including its style, design elements, construction materials, and current condition.

These features are acquired from the Algorithm Layer and are specifically the result of pre-trained AI models. To avoid long waiting times, this information is saved in the database and map view simply runs the SQL queries to acquire the results. Along with the list of features and location of the building, the user may access the text form of the AI model response and the images/street view of the building, that the model has used to extract the information mentioned above.

6.2.5.14. Clustering visualization

On the second page of the service, users are presented with a detailed analysis of the clusters constructed through advanced image processing and data analytics. This page serves as visualization of categorizations of CH buildings, highlighting the key features that have driven the clustering process. Users can explore summary statistics, both in static form and through interactive graphical representations - plots. These visualizations enable users to discern patterns and trends that are critical for effective preservation strategies. Moreover, the service leverages the insights gained from past renovation and maintenance actions within each cluster (if available) to offer tailored recommendations. By identifying which interventions have yielded positive outcomes in buildings with similar characteristics, the service helps users make data-driven decisions. These recommendations are highly tied to the unique attributes of the buildings within the cluster.

6.2.5.15. Docker

For the GIS-based service, Docker serves as a cornerstone technology, streamlining the integration and management of the Database, Algorithm, and Presentation Layers. By containerizing the database, Docker ensures a consistent and isolated environment for data storage and retrieval, regardless of the deployment stage. This consistency is achieved through Docker images, which encapsulate the database and its configurations, facilitating easy replication and distribution across various environments. This approach not only simplifies the setup and management of the database but also minimizes configuration errors and enhances the scalability and portability of the database environment.

In the context of connecting the Algorithm and Presentation Layers, Docker ensures that the application and its dependencies are consistently available across development, testing, and production. Docker containers encapsulate all necessary dependencies, enhancing security through isolation and ensuring that the application runs reliably in any environment. Docker's scalability features also enable the service to efficiently scale based on user demand, ensuring optimal performance and resource utilization. Furthermore, Docker's compatibility with Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipelines supports automated deployment processes, enhancing the overall agility and reliability of the GIS-based service.

6.3. Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios

6.3.1. Description

The service aims to assess the impact of climate change on cultural heritage (CH) buildings at city level. It focuses on the evaluation of the most relevant climate hazards affecting CH buildings in the pilot sites of the city of Jastrebarsko (Croatia), the City of Visby (Sweden), and replication in the city of Izmir (Turkey). It will calculate relevant KPIs that reflect the risk of the building stock under different climate change scenarios, thereby facilitating informed decision-making for preservation and maintenance.

The key feature of the service is the assessment of the climate hazards of extreme temperatures (including hot days and heat waves), flooding (from intense rainfall events) and wind risk (from intense wind events) on CH buildings. This involves generating simplified assessment models at city level to evaluate the probability of occurrence of such hazardous events, as well as the exposure and vulnerability of the building stock, to obtain the risk.

The service needs input data from buildings' geometries, locations and characteristics (for a higher granular level of the assessment) or alternatively, data from districts' geometries and characteristics. It also leverages data from the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), and incorporating a downscaling procedure that combines bias-correction with historical data from weather stations to develop local climate change scenarios. With CMIP6 scenario data (SSPs-RCPs, which correspond to Shared Socioeconomic Pathways and Representative Concentration Pathways) from Copernicus C3S the service will also allow to analyse the impact of the different risks under future climate change scenarios providing information on the expected losses as a consequence of each quantified risk.

The risk calculation is derived from the IPCC AR6 WGII (<https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg2/>) definition (Figure 54), which describes it as the potential for adverse consequences for human or ecological systems, recognising the diversity of values and objectives associated with such systems. It provides a framework for understanding the increasingly severe, interconnected and often irreversible impacts of climate change; and how to best reduce adverse consequences for current and future generations. In the context of climate change, risks can arise from the dynamic interactions among climate-related hazards, the exposure and vulnerability of affected human and ecological systems.

Figure 54: Determinants of risk defined by the IPCC AR6

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Thus, risk is calculated with the following equation:

$$RISK = Hazard \times Vulnerability \times Exposure$$

Understanding the hazard as the probability of occurrence of the specific climate event, the vulnerability would be determined by the socio-economic indicators defined for sensitivity and adaptive capacity, such as building age, typology, population age distribution and income levels, and the exposure (elements at risk) including the density, location and cultural heritage value of the buildings, as well as the population at risk.

The Expected Annual Losses (EAL) will be calculated to quantify the economic impact of the different climate hazards, providing a clear measure of the potential losses associated with each future scenario.

6.3.2. Service workflow

The service will be available through an interactive and user-friendly web-based tool for heritage managers, urban planners, and policy/decision-makers, helping them to make better-oriented decisions on how to mitigate the impacts of climate change on CH buildings at the city level. It will also promote sustainable and resilient heritage conservation.

Figure 55 represents the service workflow from the user perspective:

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Figure 55: Service 10 Heritage Buildings Environmental Climate Scenarios workflow

The service will be accessible through the INHERIT Platform. When the user enters, a map of the pilot appears, containing the geometries definitions for the buildings or districts/neighbourhoods at city level, depending on the level of detail of data provided. The user is able to select a climate hazard, and then the user will be able to visualise the intermediate maps with the colours for the hazard probability of occurrence, the exposure, the vulnerability and the final aggregated map with the risk assessment for the hazard. The results of the assessment of the hazard include also the Expected Annual Losses (EAL) as indicator.

The user can also evaluate the effects of climate change scenarios, selecting a scenario from those available (combined SSPs-RCPs) and a future period (short, mid and long-term). A coloured map with the risk assessment of the hazard in the defined climate scenarios will be shown, together with the indicator for Expected Annual Losses (EAL).

6.3.3. Input and Output Data

6.3.3.1. Input Data

CARTIF prepared a template to inform the pilots about the data that is crucial for the service, as well as other optional data that would enable to provide added value to the service (more detail and accuracy of the results). Pilots were requested to complete it to get to know the data availability in each one and thus the level of detail that the service may have in each of them.

Figure 56 presents the template, which includes the datasets requested and a description of the information that is needed from each of them, together with the relevance of the data (classified between high relevance – crucial data, and medium relevance – desirable data). Then, the template is expected to be completed by the pilots informing on the availability of the data (including specification in case there are any restrictions), the description of the available data (if available), the format, the access to it (if data can be downloaded, or if it is under-demand, or if a connection via API or similar is needed...). The template includes also space for additional comments just in case.

Inherit		s.10 Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios					
Service needs		Pilot data identification					
Dataset	Info needed in the data	Relevance	Availability	Description	Format	Access	Other comments
			<i>specify if any restrictions to obtain the data</i>	<i>describe the data, what it contains...</i>	<i>formats in which data is available</i>	<i>if data can be downloaded from a page, or under-demand, or by connection via API...</i>	<i>any other comment about data</i>
Cadastral data or similar	Geometries of the buildings Year of construction Typologies	HIGH crucial data					
District/ neighbourhood city structure	Name and geometry of the District/neighbourhood city structure	HIGH crucial data					
CH information	CH buildings relation or protected/ historical buildings or CH zones	MEDIUM desirable data					
Health services	Buildings for sanitary use	MEDIUM desirable data					
Weather data from meteorological stations	Historical data (ideally hourly from 30 years) on: Temperature, Precipitation, Wind	HIGH crucial data					
Weather data from sensors in the city	Temperature, precipitation, wind data with higher granularity (for urban microclimate)	MEDIUM desirable data					
Population density	At district or census level	HIGH crucial data					
Socioeconomic data at district or census level	Age distribution (-14 years old or +65) People with disabilities Income levels (household income) Employment rate Income diversity Educational level (to be more aware of climate change) Population at risk of poverty or social exclusion Energy poverty	MEDIUM desirable data					
Other data :)							

Figure 56: Service 10 Input data identification template

The cadastral data or similar is needed to have accurate geometries of the buildings, as well as to obtain the year of construction of the buildings and the typologies (relevant for the vulnerability and partly for the exposure assessment). The district or neighbourhood city structure is needed also to be able to get data at this secondary level, or alternatively to use this as main structure for the risk assessment in case no detailed data at building level is provided. The Cultural Heritage information, both on historical or protected buildings or zones, is also relevant data for the vulnerability of the buildings. For a proper assessment of the population vulnerability and exposure, economic indicators need to be considered. This needs to be defined taking into account the data available in each case. In the template, a list of potential relevant data geolocated whether possible is related to health services (e.g. buildings for sanitary use), as well as other data such as age distribution (more vulnerable people are those below 14 and over 65 years old), people with disabilities, income levels (or household income), employment rate, income diversity, educational level (relevant also for the adaptive capacity when higher awareness about climate change), people at risk of poverty or social exclusion (AROPE indicator), energy poverty data, etc. Thus, the granularity or level of detail and accuracy of the service results will be directly related to the amount and detail of the data provided.

6.3.4. Internal Architecture

The Figure 57 provides a simple visualisation of the service architecture, and depicts the main components of the service and their interactions:

Figure 57: Service 10 Heritage Buildings Environmental Climate Scenarios architecture

The **service architecture** is organised around three main components or layers, the database layer, to store all data needed; the logic layer, to process the data and calculate the results; and the presentation layer, which features the interactive web tool that offers the results in a user-friendly way.

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The **database layer** comprises three key databases, one related to climate data (Copernicus Climate Change Service, weather data from meteorological stations), buildings' data (including cadastral and OpenStreetMap, and/or other additional sources providing information on building geometries and characteristics, cultural heritage value, district or neighbourhood data), and socioeconomic data (to build the vulnerability and exposure of the buildings and citizens).

The **logic layer** involves the core computational processes, firstly for the generation of the map with the geometries and characteristics of the buildings (or districts/neighbourhoods in case of higher level). It also includes the risk calculation algorithm, which provides an assessment of the probability of occurrence of the three different hazards, the vulnerability of the buildings and citizens characterization, as well as the exposure of elements at risk mapping. The Expected Annual losses (EAL) calculation algorithm will then run, to quantify the economic impact of the climate hazards. It will be based on the results of the hazard risk and data related with the economic losses that each hazard might cause. This logic layer also involves the downscaling procedure for the data of climate change scenarios, which is a method that joins a bias correction of future climate data with historical data to generate future climate data with high-spatial resolution including the local constraints.

The **presentation layer** features an interactive web-based graphical user interface with several functionalities: the risk assessment maps, for the visualisation of the hazard risk (aggregated map), and intermediate maps for the probability of occurrence, vulnerability and exposure. The EAL indicator, to display the expected annual economic losses due to the climate hazards. And the climate change scenarios' function, that allows the user to select future climate scenarios and periods and offers visual maps showing the risk assessment under the selected scenarios.

6.3.5. Implementation

The Service will be exposed to the user through an online Graphical User Interface, which can be conveniently accessed via standard web browsers. The front-end and the back-end will be interconnected through APIs, with a PostGIS database serving as the repository for managing geolocated information.

For the front-end the technologies that probably will be used are *Angular*, supplemented by various libraries as *leaflet* (for maps) or *Plotly* and *ECharts* (for graphical representations). For the back-end *.NET* will be used, complementing with *Python* for the algorithms, and supported with other libraries as *fastAPI*. To enhance deployment and scalability, the service will be encapsulated within a Docker image, ensuring efficient and consistent deployment across diverse environments.

7. Conclusions

In this deliverable, we provided a comprehensive description of the initial iteration of the INHERIT services by outlining the development and status of the services, thus providing a detailed overview of the architectural foundation and component interactions. Our approach began with a high-level architectural view, breaking down the system's core components and explaining how different services and components interact to support the INHERIT platform's goals. Each tool's specific functionalities were detailed, covering their internal architecture, input and output data, processing workflow, and current implementation stage. The services sections aimed to clarify how they collectively contribute to the platform's overall operation.

The chosen technologies were carefully selected to align closely with the project's objectives, ensuring the platform is equipped with tools that support scalability, adaptability, and efficient data management. These technological choices were discussed in relation to their advantages for INHERIT, demonstrating why they were suitable for the platform's needs at this stage.

Given that this is the first iteration, each tool and service is designed with flexibility for future development. This deliverable represents an evolving version, intended to be iteratively improved. In the upcoming stages, we plan to include improvements and updates upon the initial design and enhance the services' functionalities. These updates and additional features will be documented in deliverable D4.2, allowing the INHERIT platform to progress steadily toward fulfilling its objectives.

Following this deliverable, the project will move into subsequent stages building upon the initial conceptual architecture presented here and the first release of the Data Exchange Platform.

Summarizing, D4.1 "First wave of INHERIT Decision support services" deliverable represents a milestone (MS 4 "1st development cycle completion") for the INHERIT project, achieving early-stage goals in architecture design, data interoperability, and decision support service development. This deliverable ensures the project is on track to meet its overarching objectives, contributing valuable insights and tools to safeguard Europe's cultural legacy sustainably.

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